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MASTER'S DEGREE IN
BIOINFORMATICS FOR COMPUTATIONAL GENOMICS

**CONSTRUCTION OF A KNOWLEDGE
GRAPH FOR RNA DRUG ANALYSIS**

Supervisor:

Prof. Marco MESITI

Co-supervisor:

Prof. Giorgio VALENTINI

Candidate:

Emanuele CAVALLERI

Student ID:

Università degli Studi di Milano – 985888

Politecnico di Milano – 995883

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Abstract

In the past 5 years, a great deal of research has been devoted to the construction of biomedical Knowledge Graphs (KGs) capturing complex hidden biological and biochemical mechanisms by integrating different data sources. KGs are rapidly being adopted by the pharmaceutical industry to accelerate data-driven drug discovery by enabling the use of powerful algorithms for different kinds of applications, ranging from prioritizing novel disease targets to predicting previously unknown drug-disease associations. On the other hand, the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the importance of RiboNucleic Acid (RNA)-based technologies for the development of new vaccines and, more in general, of novel RNA-based therapies covering the full spectrum of the main human diseases. The availability of a KG describing RNA molecules and their interaction with any other biomedical entity would therefore be a crucial resource for RNA-drug development. However, even if many open data sources report the interaction among different RNA molecules and some other biomedical entities (e.g., drugs, diseases, and genes), we still lack a comprehensive and well-described KG that contains such information.

This thesis project is rooted in the context of the “National Center for Gene Therapy and Drugs based on RNA Technology” funded by the Italian PNRR, and aims at creating a novel biomedical KG (named RNA-KG) for representing and inferring biological, experimentally validated, interactions among (coding and non-coding) RNA molecules. The construction of RNA-KG faces many interoperability issues for the acquisition of big biological data from biomolecular databanks and bio-ontologies. Starting from the analysis of public data sources containing different kinds of non-coding RNA sequences (and their relationships with other molecules), we have developed a meta-graph to guide the RNA-KG construction by exploiting and integrating biomedical ontologies and relevant data from public databases. Moreover, we propose an initial version of RNA-KG containing around 600K nodes and 6M edges, and we describe its topological characteristics.

Keywords: RNA molecules, RNA-based technologies, RNA data sources, RNA-drug discovery, Biological Knowledge Graphs

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Introduction

Knowledge Graphs (KGs) are a powerful and versatile approach for the representation of information in terms of basic entities and the relationships among them guaranteeing common semantics [97]. KGs represent the ideal method for facilitating the representation of knowledge in various fields, including education, scientific research, social media, and medical care [170]. Human diseases are the consequence of multiple molecular alterations and genetic interactions: semantically rich biomedical KGs capture this large-scale knowledge and are able to represent a map of how individual components relate to each other [241], allowing us to make sense of the underlying complexity, and infer hypotheses that can be experimentally validated.

A biomedical field of research of great relevance nowadays is RiboNucleic Acid (RNA) therapeutics, which comprises a rapidly expanding category of drugs that will change the standard of care for many diseases and actualize personalized medicine [61, 65, 184, 237, 260]. Various forms of RNA molecules may be used to selectively act on bioactive molecules and pathways that cannot be targeted by conventional drugs. RNA-based drugs represent one of the most promising advances in therapeutics, as evidenced by the recent success of mRNA-based vaccines for the COVID-19 pandemic [13]. More generally, coding and non-coding RNA molecules can potentially lead to a significant breakthrough in the therapy of cancer, genetic and neurodegenerative disorders, cardiovascular and infectious diseases [61].

Pharmaceutical R&D process is becoming more and more affected by advanced computing. Computational tools and in silico modeling are key elements for drug discovery and development. Discovery and experimentation of Imatinib (commercialized under the name of Glivec and Gleevec by Novartis) is a fundamental step in Medicine history: Imatinib is an oral chemotherapy medication used to treat cancer born not from a casual empiric experience, but designed from beginning to end “at the table”, by the means of rational drug design supported by high-throughput screening [39].

Conventional drugs show relevant limitations in their druggable targets, because they usually consist of small molecules targeting proteins, and only about 10% of proteins have druggable binding sites. On the contrary, RNA drugs can target both proteins and mRNA, as well as other non-coding RNA. Moreover, they can encode missing or defective proteins, regulate the transcriptome, and mediate DNA or RNA editing. Thus, RNA technology significantly broadens the set of druggable targets, and is also less expensive than other technologies (e.g. drug synthesis based on recombinant proteins), due to the relatively simple structure of RNA molecules that facilitates their biochemical synthesis and chemical modifications [184]. Guided by these considerations, the scientific community is now focusing on the study and development of novel RNA drugs, ranging from mRNA vaccines to small non-coding RNA therapies, such as microRNA (miRNA), small interfering RNA (siRNA), and antisense oligonucleotides (ASO) drugs, to use their therapeutic potential for a large range of relevant human diseases [61, 184]. To gather in the existing knowledge about RNA molecules (including RNA approved drugs) and then conduct RNA-drug discovery by means of innovative and cutting-edge algorithms, an RNA-centered KG should be developed that combines and maps annotations from several bio-ontologies and linked data made available in public data sources.

In the framework of the NextGenerationEU funded “National Center for Gene Therapy and Drugs based on RNA Technology”, we aim to support the discovery of novel RNA-based drugs by developing an RNA-centered KG (RNA-KG). RNA-KG will collect and organize data and knowledge about RNA molecules, retrieved from public databases and/or generated from the results of the research groups involved in the National Center. Moreover, it will provide a comprehensive description of the relationships among the various kind of RNAs, diseases, drugs, phenotypes, and other bio-medical entities. RNA-KG will be the basis for the development of novel cutting-edge AI methods specifically tailored for the analysis of various biological processes involving RNA. These methods could also open the way to RNA-drug prioritization, RNA drug-target prediction, and other prediction tasks for discovering RNA drugs for specific human diseases.

With the aim of constructing RNA-KG, in this thesis, we have first analyzed the different kinds of coding and non-coding RNA molecules that have been identified in the literature and studied relevant relationships among them and with other biomedical entities (e.g., phenotype, disease, gene). The study of the “RNA-world” has revealed fundamental to understand the biological significance behind the identified relationships because RNA molecules’ Mechanisms of Action (MoAs) can be exploited to generate new therapies and drugs that avoid many limitations of traditional drugs and can lead to the treatment, prevention, and ameliorating pathological states for a wide range of human diseases including infections, cancers, and neurological, cardiovascular, and genetic disorders.

More than 50 public databases have been identified that contain information about RNA molecules and their interaction. For these data sources, we have collected their characteristics according to the RNA molecules of interest, specifying the number of species involved, the format in which data are stored, and the presence of APIs or SPARQL endpoints for accessing the data. Moreover, biological and biomedical relationships of interest have been identified in the selected sources and mapped in the standard Relations Ontology (RO [224]). Finally, we have also identified the number of relationships that can be extracted from the considered data sources.

This information has been used for the construction of a meta-graph representing the identified RNA-KG relationships in the considered data sources and mapped to terms of RO in order to guarantee interoperability. The current RNA-KG meta-graph considers 56 relations (78 including inverse ones) involving 24 biological or biomedical entities that have been identified from 25 out of 54 selected public data sources.

Starting from this meta-graph we have moved in the construction of the KG. For this purpose we take advantage of the facilities made available by PheKnowLator [37] Python 3 Library. PheKnowLator offers tools to download, transform and/or pre-processing resources (i.e., filter data, map identifiers, and merge ontologies) into edge lists, construct KGs, and generate a wide range of outputs. PheKnowLator converts edge lists into a rich OWL-based semantic representation adding edges to the core set of ontologies, and implements a tool named OWL-NETS [36] that losslessly compresses a rich OWL-based representation into RDF. Efforts have been devoted to the mapping of identifiers coming from different data sources, to the identification of properties that enhance relationships among biological entities (e.g., a ncRNA–gene relationship occurring only in a specific cell line or tissue), and to the investigation of inclusions among data sources (i.e., databases included in larger ones or relationships repeated among unrelated databanks). Identifiers have also been examined to ground underlying concepts to bio-ontologies terms to guarantee and support standard and common semantics during the construction of RNA-KG.

Relevant topological characteristics of the generated RNA-KG (containing 625,621 nodes and 6,146,995 edges) have been extracted by means of GRAPE [40] Python 3 Library and visualized relevant subgraphs of interest. Steps towards the realization of RNA-KG including the extraction process, the meta-graph, and the characteristics of the generated KG have been reported in [43, 44].

In conclusion, by means of this thesis, we have developed a first draft of RNA-KG that can be used for conducting initial analysis the graph properties and for discovering new relationships and knowledge about the fascinating “RNA-world”.

The thesis is organized as follows. Chapter 1 describes DNA and RNA biomolecular and biochemical features focusing onto their application in the biopharmaceuticals field, mentioning advantages and open issues. Then, Chapter 2 introduces approaches developed for the construction of RNA-KG starting from different heterogeneous databases and highlights the issues that should be faced. Chapter 3 provides the methodology for the identification of the public RNA-based data sources and the main characteristics of the more than 50 data sources currently selected. Chapter 4 highlights the main types of relationships that can be extracted from the sources, introduces a meta-graph that shows the potential relationships among RNA molecules, and provides the final results of this thesis work by presenting the topological characteristics and showing graphical representations of the current instance of RNA-KG. Finally, we report our concluding remarks and next research activities.

Chapter 1

Nucleic Acid Therapeutics

Research in the past few decades has seen remarkable progress in developing nucleic acid-based therapeutics. In this chapter, we put focus on advances in synthetic biology, systems biology, computational biology, bioinformatics and nanotechnology in this field. To accomplish this task, we need to focus on molecules involved in the Central Dogma of Molecular Biological, being the focal point RiboNucleic Acid (RNA). Nucleic acids Mechanisms of Action (MoAs) can be exploited to generate new therapies and drugs for a wide range of human diseases including infections, cancers, and neurological, cardiovascular, and genetic disorders.

An extensive literature review about RNA molecules and drugs has been carried out to understand the biological significance behind the relationships among RNA sequences and between RNA molecules and other biomedical entities (e.g., phenotype, disease, gene). This information is essential for the construction of our RNA-KG. An initial overview of DNA is provided to better understand the mechanisms behind the transmission of genetic information.

This chapter is organized as follows. Section 1.1 provides an overview of the Central Dogma of Molecular Biology, spanning from the discovery of DNA and RNA molecules to the biological processes and pathways they are involved in. Section 1.2 analyzes the principal types of non-coding RNA molecules, Section 1.3 describes advantages, challenges, and open issues about DNA and RNA drugs and therapies. Relying on the content of this chapter, we have realized a video for presenting to other students of the AnacletoLAB the peculiarities of the different RNA molecules (the video is available at the following link: <https://youtu.be/QjNe0WaKKEE>).

Figure 1.1: A schematic view of the Central Dogma of Molecular Biology.

1.1 Central Dogma of Molecular Biology

The process by which the instructions in DNA are converted into functional products is named “Central Dogma of Molecular Biology” [56]. As depicted in Fig. 1.1, DNA molecules undergo two main molecular processes: replication (DNA duplication) and transcription (RNA synthesis starting from one of the two DNA strands). Then, specific RNA molecules named messenger RNAs are translated into amino acids and therefore assembled into proteins. In the remainder of this section we provide an overview of DNA and messenger RNA (mRNA) molecules.

1.1.1 DNA

Every form of life uses DNA as genetic material, and every time a cell (the biological unit of all living beings, as stated in the cell theory [204]) divides, all the genetic information has to replicate precisely (otherwise, mutations occur) to ensure hereditariness and maintenance of cell functions. All cells share a common biochemistry: they are made of carbohydrates, proteins, minerals, lipids (fats), vitamins, and nucleic acids (the biggest ones). While prokaryotic cells (e.g., bacteria and archaea) are simpler and older (the first fossils of Prokaryotic cells are known from 4 billion years ago [138]) and lack a nucleus (the prokaryotic circular DNA is packed into 1 chromosome and is not surrounded by a nuclear membrane, even if a nucleoid region is still present), in eukaryotic cells the cytoplasm contains a well-defined nucleus, enclosed by a nuclear envelope, and various organelles (e.g., mitochondria, chloroplasts, rough and smooth endoplasmatic reticula, ribosomes, golgi apparatus, lysosomes, peroxisomes, vacuoles, and glioxisomes) that execute vital functions for the cell, kept all anchored by a cytoskeleton (further subdivided into microtubules, intermediate filaments, and microfilaments [185]). Fig. 1.2a shows an illustration of an eukaryotic animal cell, whose main organelles are depicted in Fig. 1.2b.

(a) Illustration of an animal cell [131].

(b) Animal cell with its main organelles [199].

Figure 1.2: Illustrations of animal cells.

Inside the nucleus, the genetic information is stored as DNA molecules. Biochemically speaking, DNA is a polymer (i.e., a substance composed of many repeating subunits named monomers) of nucleotides. Nucleotides are made up of a nucleoside, which is a pentose sugar (in the case of DNA, deoxyribose) bonded with a nitrogenous base, and with an acid phosphate group (see Fig. 1.3b).

Under cell physiological conditions (i.e., if temperature, pH, and humidity are the ones characteristic of living cells), DNA exists as a highly stable double-stranded helix (Watson-Crick model [246] based on Rosalind-Wilkins X-ray crystallography studies [198]) whose chains carry reverse complementary information. Information is stored in a four letter alphabet fashion with four possible nitrogenous bases, whose chemical structures are depicted in Fig. 1.3a. Purines pairs only with pyrimidines, specifically adenine pairs only with thymine (which is substituted by uracil in RNA molecules), guanine instead with cytosine. Uracil and thymine share a similar chemical structure.

Fig. 1.4 depicts a DNA molecule containing long chains of nucleotide bases with hydrogen bonds. Each adenine is bonded with thymine by means of two hydrogen bonds while guanine pairs with cytosine by means of three hydrogen bonds. Hydrogen bonds are chemically easy to be broken by specific helicases, allowing the unzipping of DNA necessary for its replication by specific polymerases. Nucleotide bases are arranged in the internal part of the helix, whereas the sugar-phosphate backbone (characterized by strong phospho-diester bonds) is in the external part.

Figure 1.3: Nucleotides and nitrogenous bases chemical structures.

Figure 1.4: An illustration of a double-stranded DNA molecule [12].

1.1.2 Coding RNA - messenger RNA (mRNA)

RNA is a polymer of nucleotides (as DNA) with ribose as sugar (instead of deoxyribose) and a nitrogenous base uracil that replaces thymine; uracil matches adenine as thymine (see Fig. 1.4). Due to its chemical structure, ribose is chemically less stable than deoxyribose. Differently from DNA, RNA exists as a single strain (even if bases interact in complex tridimensional structures, often not well-known yet).

Fig. 1.5 presents a possible RNA taxonomy. The main distinction among RNA molecules is between coding and non-coding RNAs. Coding RNA is named mRNA, and is transcribed using a DNA strand as template. Transcripts that are not translated into proteins are named non-coding RNAs (ncRNAs). ncRNA molecules can be further classified into long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs, with more than 200 nucleotides) and small

Figure 1.5: RNA taxonomy.

Figure 1.6: The same transcript may lead to different proteins [84].

non-coding RNAs (sncRNAs, with less than 200 nucleotides). A detailed description of ncRNA molecules will be given in Section 1.2.

In Eukaryotes, mRNA primary transcripts (pre-mRNA) follow a cascade of biological highly regulated processes for transforming them into mature, functional mRNA molecules [242]. These steps ensure translation ability and efficiency and include capping and poly-adenylation at mRNA strands extremities, splicing, and cleavage. A gene (i.e., a sequence of DNA that encodes a functional product) contains coding (exons) and non-coding (introns) sequences, but only coding ones are included in the mature mRNA molecule. Fig. 1.6 shows that some exons of a gene may be included within the final, processed mRNA transcripts. Their translated proteins are named isoforms, and often reflect different biological functions. This process is known as alternative splicing [96].

The successful completion of each maturation step allows multiple proteins to associate and package the mRNA into an mRNA ribonucleoprotein complex (mRNP). The mRNP

is then selectively recognized and exported to the cytoplasm through nuclear pores (see Fig. 1.7) to be translated by the multiprotein complex RNA polymerase II [242]. In the cytoplasm, mature mRNA codons (i.e., sequences of three nucleotides) are read by ribosomes (see Section 1.2.1), and transformed into amino acids (see Fig. 1.8a). Amino acids are organic compounds composed by 1 central atom of carbon bonded with 1 atom of hydrogen (H), 1 amine group (-NH₂), 1 carboxylic acid group (-COOH) and 1 side chain (R, twenty side chains exist in nature, giving rise to twenty possible amino acids). Amino acids are bonded into proteins with peptide bonds.

The group of rules defining how the information of nucleotides sequence in mRNA is translated in amino acids sequence of the encoded protein is named “genetic code”. The genetic code is redundant since it contains multiple codons that specify the same amino acid. As shown in Fig. 1.8b, redundancy derives from multiple codons specifying the same amino acid. Redundancy contributes to the reduction of mutation-related risks, allowing many mutations to be “silent” [58]. AUG codon specifies the amino acid methionine (Met), and establishes the reading frame for the ribosome to follow, adding corresponding amino acids in a protein. Stop codons do not specify any amino acid and signal the termination of the translation process of the current protein. Three stop codons exist: UAA, UGA, and UAG, and are named amber, opal, and ochre.

Fig. 1.7 shows a complete view at a molecular level of the Central Dogma of Molecular Biology that includes mRNA, transfer RNA and ribosomal RNA molecules (see Sections 1.2.2 and 1.2.1 for further details about these two categories of ncRNA molecules). The DNA template strand is transcribed into a pre-mRNA molecule which exits a nuclear pore and is post-transcriptionally modified to become mature mRNA (a human nuclear pore complex is here represented by a composite structure obtained using cryogenic electron microscopy [147]). Mature mRNA is translated to a protein seeping into a ribosome where codons are matched by amino-acyl charged tRNA molecules anticodons and the peptidic sequence is joint by means of peptide bonds.

Figure 1.7: Complete view at a molecular level of the Central Dogma [238].

(a) Structure of amino acids, bonded with peptide bonds into proteins [55].

		Second letter					
		U	C	A	G		
First letter	U	UUU } Phe UUC } UUA } Leu UUG }	UCU } UCC } Ser UCA } UCG }	UAU } Tyr UAC } UAA Stop UAG Stop	UGU } Cys UGC } UGA Stop UGG Trp	U	C
	C	CUU } CUC } Leu CUA } CUG }	CCU } CCC } Pro CCA } CCG }	CAU } His CAC } CAA Gln CAG }	CGU } CGC } Arg CGA } CGG }	U	C
	A	AUU } AUC } Ile AUA } AUG Met	ACU } ACC } Thr ACA } ACG }	AAU } Asn AAC } AAA Lys AAG }	AGU } Ser AGC } AGA } Arg AGG }	U	C
	G	GUU } GUC } Val GUA } GUG }	GCU } GCC } Ala GCA } GCG }	GAU } Asp GAC } GAA Glu GAG }	GGU } GGC } Gly GGA } GGG }	U	C
						A	G
						Third letter	

(b) The genetic code [129].

Figure 1.8: Amino acids, proteins, and genetic code.

1.2 Non-coding RNA

Eukaryotes have low gene density. Around 98% of human genome is non-coding, and around 30% of the coding part is devoted to DNA maintenance and integrity, resulting in a drop to about 0.8% [98] in mature tissues. Being only a small rate of the human genome corresponding to protein-coding genes, recent studies have focused their attention on the non-coding part of our transcriptome [65].

The wide variety of ncRNA molecules is involved in several cellular biological processes, including: translation processes, RNA interference pathways (RNAi, see Fig. 1.9), modification of other RNA molecules (e.g., splicing and self-cleavage processes), catalysis of biochemical reactions (i.e., enzymatic activity), and targeted gene editing. In RNAi, sncRNA forms a cytoplasmic RNA-protein complex named RNA-Induced Silencing Complex (RISC), whose catalytic component cleaves target mRNA bonded by complementary base pairing mechanism (similarly to what occurs in DNA double helix, see Fig. 1.4), after target mRNA exited the nucleus through a nuclear pore. These properties are suitable for treating pathologies with established genetic targets related to human cancer or genetic disorders [258], and will be discussed in Section 1.3.2.

In the remainder of the section, we will discuss the main kinds of non-coding molecules that can be identified in a cell and for which it is possible to extract sequences in a laboratory and used in the definition of therapies.

1.2.1 Ribosomal RNA (rRNA)

rRNA is a sncRNA which, with specific ribosomal proteins, forms ribosomes, cellular organelles in which protein synthesis occurs. Ribosomes are composed by small and large subunits, in which mature mRNA codons seep in to get bonded with amino-acyl tRNA molecules (see Section 1.2.2). Ribosomal RNA is the predominant form of RNA found in most cells (about 80% of cellular RNA is rRNA [253]).

1.2.2 Transfer RNA (tRNA)

tRNA molecules are characterized by a cloverleaf structure due to complementary base pairing (similarly to what happens in DNA double helix, see Section 1.1.1), here depicted in Fig. 1.10, consisting of an acceptor stem that covalently attaches a particular amino acid (amino-acyl tRNA, this process is catalysed by enzymes called amino-acyl tRNA synthetases) and of an anticodon sequence of three bases complementary to the corresponding mRNA codon on the opposite site, thus assuring the translation from the mRNA codon triplets to the corresponding sequence of amino acids [56].

A large number of the individual nucleotides in a tRNA molecule may be chemically

Figure 1.9: RNAi is a process in which sncRNA molecules activate a cellular response able to destroy a specific mRNA [207].

modified, often by methylation or deamidation. These unusual bases sometimes affect the tRNA's interaction with ribosomes and sometimes occur in the anticodon to alter base-pairing properties [110].

1.2.3 tRNA-derived fragment (tRF)

tRF molecules constitute sncRNA molecules generated by specific cleavage of tRNA transcripts under the spotlight of scientific community due to their size and similarity to miRNA molecules. The molecular mechanism and the ribonucleases that participate to the cleavage of tRNAs producing tRF molecules are still quite unclear [81]. Based on the incision loci, tRFs are divided into five subtypes: tRF-5, tRF-3, tRF-2, tRF-1, and internal-tRF (i-tRF). tRF-5 molecules are known to be found in the nucleus whereas tRF-3 and tRF-1 molecules are predominantly gathered in the cytoplasm [261]. tRF molecules interact with Argonaute protein members (e.g., AGO2) to form complexes participating in RNAi pathways that promote genome integrity and avoid potential threats to cellular homeostasis (e.g., silencing of transposons, retrotransposons and repeat sequences or regulation of crucial oncogenes and tumor suppressors) [65].

1.2.4 Small nucleolar and nuclear RNA (snoRNA and snRNA)

Proteins called Transcription Factors (TFs) regulate as activators or repressors the transcription process, but regulation can also be achieved at epigenetic level [228] or by ncRNA molecules. snRNA and snoRNA molecules are sncRNA molecules that primarily guide chemical modifications of other RNA molecules, mainly rRNAs, tRNAs and

Figure 1.10: tRNA cloverleaf structure [169].

themselves. They are also associated with control of chromatin compaction and accessibility [69]. Besides their role in modification and maturation of RNA, strong evidence has emerged concerning their potential role in human malignancies [65].

1.2.5 Long non-coding RNA (lncRNA)

lncRNA molecules are ncRNA transcripts greater than 200 nucleotides in length. lncRNAs are the majority of transcription products [226] and play a pivotal role in disease development and progression [76] by regulating gene transcription. They can be exonic, intergenic, in enhancer regions, or in regions distal to protein-coding genes [156]. Similar to mRNAs, lncRNAs are transcribed by RNA polymerase II (RNAPol II), carry single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) often associated with tumor risk, can undergo alternative splicing, may have 5' caps, and are usually polyadenylated [133]. Moreover, lncRNAs recruit and guide proteins involved in modifying chromatin structure [31]. From a clinical aspect, lncRNAs serve as novel promising therapeutic targets since their dysregulation is correlated with the prognosis and diagnosis of a plenty number of cancer types. Targeting lncRNAs using a variety of technologies, including ASO-based strategies (see Section 1.2.10), siRNAs (see Section 1.2.8) and small molecular inhibitors should be evaluated for their effects on tumor initiation, progression or metastasis and response to therapy [65].

Figure 1.11: Three types of circRNA molecules [195].

1.2.6 Circular RNA (circRNA)

circRNA molecules are lncRNA molecules produced from alternative splicing events, and may play a role as splicing event regulators. Differentially expressed circRNAs are involved in many human illnesses, including cancer and neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease, and strongly interfere with snRNA functions [153]. Fig. 1.11 depicts circRNAs that can be generated from backsplicing of exons, introns, or both. Accordingly, they are classified into three types [195]:

1. EcircRNAs, that are composed of exons. They are predominately cytoplasmic, may harbor miRNA response elements and serve as miRNA sponges;
2. ElciRNAs, that are circularized with introns retained between the exons;
3. CiRNAs, that are composed of introns. Both of ElciRNAs and ciRNAs are abundant in the nucleus and may play functional roles on gene transcription and post-transcription.

1.2.7 MicroRNA (miRNA)

miRNA molecules are a superfamily of genome-derived snRNA molecules governing post-transcriptional gene regulation, being associated with RNAi. Fig. 1.12 shows how a miRNA sequence acts by blocking translation or promoting degradation of target mRNAs. Inside the miRNA-mRNA-AGO2 (the last one being the catalytic core of the RISC) complex, mismatches can occur since the recognition of a target mRNA by miRNA does not require perfect base pairing [137], resulting in simultaneous regulation of the expression and the activity of hundreds of protein-coding genes and transcription factors. The same miRNA sequence can thus bind to many mRNA molecules and be involved in many different pathways. Through the control of multiple genes involved in

Figure 1.12: miRNA molecules complex with AGO2 [51].

the same biological processes, many miRNAs have been shown to play important roles in pathogenesis of human diseases, including lethal cancers.

More than 1,900 miRNAs have been identified in humans [143], together with miRNA molecules from various exogenous sources, which are present in human circulation, that are named xeno-miRNAs [227]. Canonical biogenesis of miRNAs starts from the transcription of miRNA-coding sequences by RNA polymerase II to long primary miRNA (pri-miRNA) transcripts within the nucleus. The pri-miRNA is then cleaved to shorter precursor miRNA (pre-miRNA) by the RNase III Drosha. After being transported into the cytoplasm, pre-miRNAs are cleaved, double-stranded miRNA duplexes by cytoplasmic. The miRNA duplex associated with RNA-induced silencing complex (RISC) is then unwound to offer two strands, among which the guide strand mature miRNA binds to the target mRNA through partial complementary base pairings, leading to translational inhibition or transcript degradation or cleavage [179] (acting as “molecular scissors”).

1.2.8 Small interfering RNA (siRNA)

siRNA molecules are RNA molecules arranged in a double-stranded fashion (similarly to DNA complementary base pairing between the two helices) with a molecular weight of approximately 13 kDa that suppress protein translation by recruiting RISC [184]. The endoribonuclease Dicer trims double-stranded siRNA molecules and separates the two strands within the RISC. One of the two cleaved strands acts on its targeted mRNA through perfect complementary base pairings (differently from miRNA molecules, see Section 1.2.7), leading to a sequence-specific cleavage of the targeted mRNA by the AGO2 endonuclease and consequently the knockdown of target gene. Because RISC is solely located within cytoplasm [260], siRNAs are effective in knocking down cytoplasmic targets.

1.2.9 Short or small hairpin RNA (shRNA)

shRNA molecules are artificial RNA molecules with a hairpin turn that can be used to silence target gene expression via RNAi. shRNAs follows a biogenesis pathway similar to miRNA molecules [197], and, as in siRNAs, one strand derived from the double stranded shRNA is loaded into the RISC to silence target gene expression.

1.2.10 AntiSense Oligonucleotides (ASO)

ASO are chemically synthesized, single-stranded oligonucleotides (i.e., short sequences of nucleic acids) with a molecular weight of 6–9 kDa, that selectively inhibit target gene expression via RNAi [184]. Their natural counterpart, antisense RNA (asRNA), is present in virtually all species and they are recognized for their critical functions in post-transcriptional gene regulation [210]. ASOs can act through three mechanisms of action [184], shown in Fig. 1.13. First, similar to siRNAs, ASOs bind mRNA via Watson–Crick base pairing, but unlike siRNAs, the ASO DNA–RNA heteroduplex recruits RNase H1 rather than RISC. RNase H1-dependent ASOs are also known as gapmers and lead to cleavage of the target mRNA and to the knockdown of targeted gene expression. Second, ASOs can also interfere with splicing machinery by interacting with pre-mRNA, thereby promoting alternative splicing and increasing target protein expression. However, these two mechanisms require nuclear delivery (which we remark is harder to achieve than cytoplasmic one). ASOs are effective to knock down nuclear targets likely due to the fact that RNases H and P are highly abundant in the nucleus (RISCs instead are present within the cytoplasm). The third mode, which causes downregulation of mRNA expression, is the translational arrest of the targeted protein through binding with the translation initiation codon of the target mRNA.

1.2.11 Piwi-interacting RNA (piRNA)

piRNA molecules are 21–36 nucleotides single stranded RNA molecules and represent the largest group of sncRNAs in animal cells [65]. They are abundant in spermatogenic cells and they have been found to be critically involved in germline development and functions [7]. Instead of targeting transcripts directly (as done by miRNA, siRNA, and ASO molecules), piRNAs interact with Piwi proteins, a subfamily of Argonaute proteins, to mediate epigenetic silencing. Similarly to tRFs (see Section 1.2.3), piRNAs are mainly responsible for preserving genome integrity through the silencing of transposable elements. Biogenesis of piRNAs has not been fully understood yet, thus several mechanisms have been proposed [65]. Being piRNAs functional RNA molecules implicated in gene silencing, the interest in defining their potential role in human malignancies is constantly raising in molecular biology and pharmacology research fields [65].

Figure 1.13: The three main MoAs in ASO molecules [108].

1.2.12 RNA aptamer

RNA aptamers are short single-stranded nucleic acids that can bind with high specificity and affinity to variety of targets (e.g., proteins, peptides, carbohydrates, DNA, and RNA) by virtue of their tertiary structure, rather than its sequence [177]. Aptamers have great potential to replace monoclonal antibodies in therapeutic and diagnostic applications because they can be produced via chemical synthesis, are more cost-effective in manufacturing, simpler to modify to increase metabolic stability and improve PK properties, and elicit little immunogenicity. However, despite the fact that aptamers have many advantages over antibodies, their clinical translation is challenging due to suboptimal pharmacokinetic properties (i.e., highly sensitivity to nucleases, readily excretion by kidneys) [267].

1.2.13 Riboswitch

Riboswitches are sncRNA molecules commonly found in bacteria involved in self-cleavage processes that cause gene expression control and mRNA degradation, critical for survival of the cell [157]. Functional riboswitches have been discovered in archaea, plants and fungi and may provoke alternative splicing [83].

Figure 1.14: RNA aptamer molecules bind with target biomarkers by means of their tertiary structure [25].

Figure 1.15: MoA of a hammerhead ribozyme [5].

1.2.14 Ribozyme

Ribozymes (a crasis for *ribonucleic enzymes*) are a class of sncRNA molecules that possess enzymatic activity therefore catalyzing biochemical reactions (e.g., transesterification reactions, hydrolysis of phosphodiester bonds, mRNA and protein cleavage). The hammerhead or hairpin structures facilitate a ribozyme to cleave target RNAs in specific sequences [260]. Ribosomes, the biological organelles that translate RNA into proteins, being composed by rRNA combined to specific proteins, are ribozymes.

Hammerhead ribozymes, depicted in Fig. 1.15, is a particular type of ribozyme that has two binding arms designed to bind to the complementary RNA targets in a Watson-Crick pairing. This ribozyme binds to its target mRNA and makes an mRNA-ribozyme

Figure 1.16: gRNA guides Cas9 nuclease to cut defined genomic portions [202].

complex. The catalytic motif of the ribozyme then cleaves its target RNA into pieces, thus inhibiting gene expression. After cleaving the RNA target, the ribozyme becomes free again to enter into the next cycle.

Furthermore, ribozymes were the center of a presumed RNA world in the early origin of life [171]. It might be imagined that all of the components of RNA were available in some prebiotic pool, and that these components assembled into replicating, evolving polynucleotides without the prior existence of any evolved macromolecules [205]. Ribozymes would have perfectly suited such an environment, carrying the genetic information to be transmitted to the offspring but also having enzymatic activity to adapt to this framework.

1.2.15 Guide RNA (gRNA)

gRNA sequences are complementary to target DNA or mRNA leading to complementary base pairing and form complexes with enzymes such as CRISPR associated nucleases (Cas) in bacteria [112] (see Fig. 1.16).

The CRISPR/Cas-based gene editing mechanism relies on two essential components, a designed gRNA and the RNA-guided Cas nuclease. Through its hairpin scaffolding to Cas to form Cas-gRNA ribonucleoprotein (RNP) complex in the nucleus, the gRNA recognizes a Protospacer-Adjacent Motif (PAM) element in the genome through complementary base pairings and thus directs the Cas nuclease to generate a double-stranded DNA break or a single-stranded break (nick) to achieve genome engineering [260]. PAM is a 2–6 nucleotide long DNA sequence immediately following the DNA sequence targeted by the Cas9 nuclease in the CRISPR bacterial adaptive immune system.

1.3 Nucleic Acid Therapies and Drugs

Therapeutic DNA and RNA molecules can mediate the sequence-specific recognition of endogenous nucleic acids through Watson-Crick base pairing, which can also be targeted by several types of small molecules (e.g., antibiotics). Moreover, nucleic acids are essential for cells to synthesize proteins, which exploit vital functions for any organism (e.g., energetic, immune, structural, transport, enzymatic, hormonal, signaling, and contractile functions). DNA and RNA molecules also regulate, silence gene expression, or selectively act on biological entities (e.g., proteins, transcripts, genes) and pathways that cannot be targeted by conventional small molecules or proteins. All these properties can be addressed in the generation of nucleic acid-based therapies and drugs

In this section, we describe in detail the biological and pharmaceutical purposes and relevance of nucleic acids. We focus our attention on nucleic acid drug delivery, advantages, and open issues of this technology.

1.3.1 DNA therapeutics

DNA-based biopharmaceuticals aim at generate therapeutic proteins that replace defective or missing protein(s) [213] once the DNA sequence of choice is delivered to the nuclei of the patient's cells and at control disease progression by induction and/or inhibition of genes. DNA-based drugs have attracted the attentions of the scientific community on computational predictions that allows to select candidate molecules basing onto high selectivity and specificity recognition of their molecular targets and pathways. This can be achieved by modeling the DNA sequence and structure of choice by means of high-throughput systems, leading to a reduced potential for toxicity and side effects and a higher chance of potent molecules with specific activity. DNA-based drugs have emerged in recent years to yield extremely promising candidates for drug therapy for a wide range of diseases, including cancer, AIDS, neurological disorders such as Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer's disease, and cardiovascular disorders [183]. In addition, starting from genomic data and the study of single-nucleotide polymorphisms, genome editing tools are used to add, remove or alter the genetic material at particular locations in the genome, allowing personalized medicine.

Another remarkable example of DNA-based drug is INOVIO vaccine. This vaccine encodes the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 to induce immunity to the virus after intramuscular injection [107], and belongs to the DNA vaccines category. In general, DNA-based vaccines encode specific antigen(s) to induce a protective immune response [60], and may also target infectious agents.

DNA drugs may be delivered as plasmids or integrated into a viral vector [61]. The

plasmid DNA (pDNA) must penetrate the cytoplasmic and nuclear membranes to gain access to the nucleus. In the nucleus, pDNA is transcribed into mRNA that encodes the desired protein in the patient's body [218] (see Section 1.1.2). Therapeutic DNA can also be transfected through a viral vector (e.g., Adeno-Associated virus [236]) into the cells *ex vivo* to alter cell phenotype or function, and then these cells are expanded and delivered into the patient [60].

DNA-based drugs are commonly affected by poor biological stability (compensated by advances in chemical synthesis), a short half-life, DNA degradation by aspecific DNAses and a random delivery profile, resulting in unpredictable pharmacokinetics' properties. Furthermore, concerns regarding integration of foreign DNA into the host chromosomes and disruption of normal gene function exist [139]. These limitations can be addressed by RNA therapeutics, topic of Section 1.3.2.

1.3.2 RNA therapeutics

RNA therapeutics first gained attention in 1978, when Paul Zamecnik reported that a synthetic 13-mer oligonucleotide complementary to the viral mRNA could inhibit replication of Rous sarcoma virus [262]. Diverse RNA molecules have been used to interfere with potential therapeutic targets (mainly genes, RNAs, and proteins), and their properties resulting interesting for developing new medications. The development of RNA therapeutics is expected to expand the range of druggable targets, including conventional proteins and previously undrugged or "undruggable" transcripts and genes [260].

In the remainder, we analyze in details pharmaceutical relevance of RNA molecules by applying the classification in coding (mRNA therapeutics) and non-coding sequences (ncRNA therapeutics). Moreover, we discuss how RNA drugs can be ferried and safely entrapped into exogenous cells and tissues, which are the main advantages with respect to DNA therapeutics. Finally, we discuss open issues in this field.

mRNA therapeutics

The development and use of mRNA molecules as a novel class of drug has great potential in vaccination, protein replacement therapy, and antibody therapy for the treatment of a wide variety of human diseases, including infections, cancers, and genetic disorders [260]. Different from plasmid DNA (pDNA) or virus-based gene therapy, mRNA drugs are translated into target proteins by the endogenous cellular machinery (see Section 1.1 and Fig. 1.7) without interfering with the genome: mRNA strands can be transfected into the cells *ex vivo* to introduce defective proteins. They also do not need to enter the nucleus for translation, unlike pDNA vaccines that require nuclear localization to elicit their protective effects. On the other side, mRNA drugs are much bigger

than other types of RNA molecules and, because of their size, mRNA sequences are in vitro transcribed and cannot currently be made with site-specific chemical modifications using solid-state synthesis. Modifications can be applied to the ribose and phosphate moieties to reduced nuclease-mediated degradation as well as off-target mRNA binding in order to enhance silencing in vivo [260].

Moreover, mRNA therapeutics hold great promise as vaccines for the treatment of infectious and cancerous diseases. mRNA can mediate expression of an antigen, encode a target protein in order to evoke and elicit long-lasting protective immunity against the antigen itself (prophylactic vaccines), or harness the immune system to fight cancer (therapeutic vaccines). Recently, COVID-19 mRNA vaccines, created by Moderna and Acuitas/BioNTech/Pfizer, have shown how effective it is to invest on RNA therapeutics. As depicted in Fig. 1.17, intramuscular injections of liposomes (i.e., a small artificial spherical lipidic vesicles), carrying the mRNA sequence encoding the spike protein of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, reduce infection, morbidity and spread caused by COVID-19 disease [67]. The cellular translation apparatus recognizes the exogenous mRNA as endogenous (chemical modifications at mRNA sequence level are needed, e.g., pseudouridylation) and starts to translate it into a spike protein. The just translated spike protein is recognized by the immune system which develops antibodies against it. Currently, there are three major biopharmaceutical companies that develop mRNA therapeutics: Moderna (Boston, MA, United States), CureVac (Tubingen, Germany), and BioNTech (Mainz, Germany) [61].

Orally bioavailable small molecules have also been identified to directly interact with pre-mRNA molecules to modulate splicing [50]. This strategy is feasible for the treatment of genetic disorders, especially those diseases caused by errors during the splicing process (e.g., intron retention or exon skipping).

Finally, mRNA therapeutics allow to express significantly higher amount of antigen with lower doses of mRNA by self-amplifying RNA vaccines containing an antigen-encoding sequence followed by a viral RNA dependent RNA polymerase-encoding sequence along with other elements required for replication. In addition, the genetic sequences dictating disease initiation and progression may be directly changed by using proper gRNAs and other necessary components to achieve eradication of the disease.

ncRNA therapeutics

ncRNA molecules can target intracellular mRNAs or functional ncRNAs through complementary base pairings, leading to gene silencing or control of gene expression for the treatment of diseases. The various types of ncRNAs presented in Section 1.2 may have different applications in the pharmaceutical field. Examples of therapeutics are

Figure 1.17: mRNA vaccine against the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 [178].

reported in the remainder of the section for each type of ncRNA molecule (highlighted in **bold**) whose MoAs are indeed exploited in the construction of drugs.

The **miRNA**-based therapeutics could be categorized into two types: miRNAs mimics and miRNAs inhibitors [61]. The former are double-stranded RNA molecules that mimic miRNAs, while the latter are single-stranded RNA oligonucleotides designed to interfere with miRNAs. Synthetic miRNA mimics restore some tumor-suppressive miRNAs lost in cancer cells [260]: this “miRNA replacement therapy” strategy is of particular interest since miRNAs are endogenous components and reintroduced miRNAs may be well tolerable in cells [260]. Unlike siRNAs (see Section 1.2.8), each miRNA can simultaneously regulate the expression of multiple transcripts (see Sec. 1.2.7, specifically Fig. 1.12). When it comes to build miRNA strategies for the pharmaceuticals, this property can result in adverse events (e.g., targeting a house-keeping gene). As of today, no miRNA drug has been FDA-approved. Efforts were also made to explore small-molecule inhibitors against the biogenesis of oncogenic miRNA sequences with complementary oligonucleotides [260].

siRNA therapeutics relies on the fact that, due to its small number of nucleotides, scientists can use solid-phase synthesis to manufacture siRNA molecules. Second, siRNA

Figure 1.18: ASO (black strand) complexed with ADAR [48].

utilizes RISC, which is endogenous to eukaryotic cells and thus does not require the delivery of large enzymes with nuclease domains. Finally, given that siRNA interferes with mature mRNA, it requires only cytoplasmic delivery, which is easier to achieve than nuclear delivery. siRNAs have been approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) in the form of the following drugs: patisiran [201], which is used to treat polyneuropathy caused by hereditary TTR-mediated amyloidosis (hATTR); givosiran [9], which is used to treat acute hepatic porphyria; lumasiran [79]), which is used to treat primary hyperoxaluria type 1; and inclisiran [196], which is used to treat hypercholesterolaemia. siRNA drugs under clinical development are also expanded to other therapeutic areas, including oncology, that impact millions of patients. For instance, synthetic siRNA targeting a protein-tyrosine kinase named ephrin type-A receptor 2 (EphA2) was shown to be effective in controlling tumor growth in xenograft mouse models [181]. Finally, recent in vitro studies have shown that *shRNA* molecules, usually introduced into cells through viral vectors or pDNA produces fewer off-target effects than siRNA [197].

To date, three **ASO** drugs have received FDA approval: Nusinersen [175] is used to treat spinal muscular atrophy (SMA); Eteplirsen [1] is used to treat Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD); Inotersen [74] is used to treat familial amyloid polyneuropathy caused by the mutation in the transthyretin (TTR) gene. Furthermore, chemically modified ASOs

have been designed with an engineered hairpin domain that recruits the endogenous RNA-editing enzyme adenosine deaminase acting on RNA (ADAR) [48]. Fig. 1.18 depicts an ASO-ADAR complex, which chemically converts adenosines to inosines which are subsequently read as guanosine by the endogenous translational machinery, leading to adenosine to inosine to guanine mRNA editing. Editing via ASO-ADAR strategies represent an emerging class of RNA therapeutics for treating genetic disease [166].

RNA aptamers can directly bind to extracellular, cell surface, or intracellular proteins that are traditionally targeted by small-molecule and protein drugs. In 2004, pegaptanib [134] was the first RNA aptamer drug approved by the FDA for treating age-related macular degeneration, a leading cause of irreversible blindness worldwide.

The prokaryotic component of the **gRNA**-related adaptive immune system CRISPR/Cas has been adapted as a novel and accessible technology to precisely edit genome sequence toward irreversible knockout or knockin of a target gene in mammalian cells and organisms as compared with RNAi, which does not completely eradicate gene expression, and mRNA therapy, which transiently introduces functional proteins [164]. As such, the CRISPR/Cas technology has been actively evaluated toward the development of new therapies for the treatment of human diseases, including monogenetic disorders, infection, and cancer [229].

ncRNAs can also target other RNA. For instance, synthetic **ribozymes** have been designed to target viral RNA: a ribozyme directed against HIV RNA has entered clinical testing [216]. Similarly, ribozymes have been designed to target the hepatitis C virus RNA [142], SARS-CoV-2 [68], and influenza virus RNA [233]. Furthermore, RNA molecules can also be the target for other bio-active molecules or chemical compounds. Discovery of the mechanistic actions of antibiotics on ribosomes (composed by proteins and **rRNA** subunits, see Section 1.2.1) is a major driver for the discovery and development of RNA-targeted drugs. Aminoglycoside antibiotics, such as the macrolide named erythromycin (macrolides are large macrocyclic esters – i.e., lactones – with a 14-, 15-, or 16-membered ring), whose complex chemical structure is reported in Fig. 1.19a, directly bind to rRNA in order to inhibit protein synthesis by blocking the nascent polypeptide exit site [190] (see Fig. 1.19b). Erythromycin is an antibiotic approved for the treatment of a number of bacterial infections of the skin and upper respiratory tract [190].

Besides antibiotics, there are also many other small molecules under clinical and preclinical development that act on existing and new RNA targets for the treatment of various human diseases, including genetic disorders, infections, and cancers. RNAs are often folded into secondary (e.g., helices or stems, loops, and bulges), tertiary (e.g., junctions, pseudoknot, and motifs), and quaternary (e.g., complexes) structures; thus, small-mol-

Figure 1.19: Erithromycin chemical structure and MoA.

ecule compounds have the potential to directly interact with unique higher-order structures rather than the primary sequences [173]. **Riboswitch** sequences have emerged as potential therapeutic targets because they are highly structured to form unique ligand binding pockets and function as gene regulatory factors, similar to the structural and functional selectivity of proteins [157]. Fig. 1.20 shows SAM/SAH riboswitch predicted pocket, suitable as drug target. A new field of research is the development of small-molecule inhibitors against SARS-CoV-2 well conserved RNA pseudoknot motif for the treatment of pandemic severe acute respiratory syndrome [91]. In general, viral genomes consist of some highly conserved RNA elements that play pivotal roles in gene regulation and viral replication named motifs [260]. Being highly structured, viral RNA motifs have emerged as potential targets for the development of small-molecule and ncRNA antiviral drugs and vaccines [92].

Thus far, a number of strategies have been developed and used to design and/or identify small molecules that can bind to RNA targets, such as binding- or phenotype-based screening and computational modeling and structure- or cheminformatics-based design or virtual screening; target-directed approaches and tools that can be used to identify RNA-binding compounds and the chemical knowledge are reported in [88]. Site-specific chemical modifications can influence the MoA of ncRNAs, as well as the target sequence binding affinity [184]. Phosphate backbone and sugar rings are usually chemically modified to improve the metabolic stability and pharmacokinetics properties, potency, specificity, and to achieve long-lasting gene silencing while minimizing off-target effects [184].

Figure 1.20: SAM/SAH riboswitch structure [247]. Abbreviation: SD – predicted Shine-Dalgarno sequence.

In addition, specific ligands, such as hepatocyte asialoglycoprotein receptor-binding N-acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc), may be covalently attached to ncRNA molecules to achieve cell- or organ-selective gene silencing [260]. GalNAc exhibits several traits that make it an ideal targeting ligand. For instance, it has a molecular weight lower than 2 kDa, which ensures that most of the drug being administered is the ncRNA of choice and not GalNAc.

RNA drugs delivery

Irrespective of their therapeutic MoA, the large size of some therapeutic RNAs, such as mRNAs, their anionic charge, and their susceptibility to RNases present in both the bloodstream and tissues make it difficult for therapeutic RNA to enter cells efficiently and function on its own. To overcome the barriers to safe and effective RNA delivery, scientists have developed both viral-vector-based and non-viral delivery systems that protect the RNA from degradation, maximize delivery to on-target cells and minimize exposure to off-target cells. RNA can be ferried into cells using non-viral drug delivery systems, which circumvent the limitations of viral delivery vectors, synthetic materials that encapsulate RNA, such as polymer-based, lipid-based nanoparticles as occurs in mRNA SARS-CoV-2 vaccines (see Fig. 1.17), and conjugate-based drug delivery systems, or even by using antibody fragments or antibodies to target cell types [184].

RNA drugs advantages and open issues

RNA therapeutics, including RNA molecules as drugs and RNA-targeted small molecules, comprise a rapidly expanding category of drugs that will change the standard of care for many diseases and actualize personalized medicine. These drugs are cost

effective, relatively simple and rapid to manufacture compared to small molecules and recombinant proteins, adapt sequence for personalized treatments to new pathogens (e.g. SARS-CoV-2 new variants), and various forms of RNAs may be used to selectively act on proteins, transcripts, and genes that cannot be targeted by DNA drugs, conventional small molecules or proteins without the risk of chromosomal integration [155]. This makes these drugs suitable for pathologies with established genetic targets, including infectious diseases, cancers, immune diseases, and Mendelian disorders (including neurological disorders) [184].

Moreover, recombinant proteins have limitations as drugs, particularly due to size and stability issues [4]. Furthermore, they must be properly folded and often require post-translational modifications [217] that complicate the synthetic process. By contrast, nucleic-acid based strategies avoid many of these limitations as they make use of the translational machinery of the mammalian cell.

On the other hand, exogenous RNA molecules are prone to endosomal trapping and hydrolysis by non-specific RNases that are highly abundant in the blood, and are required to pass the cellular membrane barriers (RNA molecules are negatively charged) to access intracellular targets [260]. Similar to protein therapeutics (e.g., insulin [268], trastuzumab [29], and pembrolizumab [130]), RNA drugs (e.g., mipomersen [20] and patisiran [201]) are not orally bioavailable; hence, both RNA and protein drugs are usually administered to patients via other routes, such as intravenous or subcutaneous injection. After the identification of an RNA candidate drug, or the selection of proper drug-like small molecules targeting RNA molecules, the RNA candidate drug may be processed for further preclinical and clinical investigations to improve efficacy, potency, binding affinity and selectivity toward defined target(s), and safety profiles (e.g., avoid possible cytotoxicity or acute immune response such as cytokine release).

Chapter 2

Approaches for the Construction of Biomedical KGs

Biological KGs are usually constructed by integrating information generated by different research institutes and the usual data integration issues (use of different data models, formats, and semantics) need to be faced. Specifically, data redundancies, data duplicates, and lack of common identifier mechanisms must be properly addressed. In the case of RNA-KG, we also have to consider the lack of specific ontologies for the description of all possible non-coding RNA sequences, and the presence of bio-ontologies that are not well-recognized by the community because still in their infancy.

The purpose of this chapter is to introduce the concept of KGs and their role in the context of biomedical applications. Moreover, since biomedical KGs are usually represented and organized according to specific biomedical ontologies, we first introduce the concept of Ontology and provide an overview of the main kinds of biomedical ontologies that are useful for the construction of our RNA-KG. Finally, we present tools and approaches for the acquisition of data from heterogeneous data sources and their transformation into knowledge graphs that adhere to the constraints imposed by biomedical ontologies. The concepts and technologies introduced in this chapter will be exploited in the next chapter for the construction of RNA-KG.

This chapter is organized as follows. Section 2.1 aims at describing KGs from a logical and structural point of view. Section 2.2 defines the concept of ontology, and introduces the most used biological and biomedical ontologies. Then, Section 2.3 describes different approaches for the construction and population of KG. Finally, Section 2.4 shows examples of biomedical applications of KGs.

2.1 Knowledge graphs

KGs are a powerful and versatile approach for representing information in terms of basic entities and the relationships among them guaranteeing common semantics. KGs are logical structures able to facilitate the knowledge representation in specific domains, through a graph structure composed of a set of nodes, representing the domain concepts, and a set of edges, representing the different kinds of relationships that can exist among the nodes [97]. KGs are thus an approach for the representation of knowledge in a given domain. Moreover, they also provide tools for reasoning on such knowledge, and finding new relations not directly related. Representations of knowledge would be sterile without knowledge-based inference [105] that can be implemented in software and automatically processed exploiting transitive properties among related concepts.

A KG is usually represented through RDF triples [19] which indicates that an entity *subject*, usually identified by a persistent identifier, is connected through a relation/property to an *object*. The object can be an entity or a basic property of the subject. Persistent identifiers avoid identity ambiguity and naming clashes when the KG is extended with external data. Prominent examples of persistent identifiers include Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for papers, ORCID iDs for authors, International Standard Book Numbers (ISBNs) for books, and Internationalised Resource Identifiers (IRIs). Since persistent identifiers can be arbitrary, they will sometimes have a non-human-interpretable form: to address this issue it is common to add RDF edges that provide a human-interpretable label for nodes (e.g. NCBI gene *1954* labeled as *MEGF8*, its gene symbol) in a process named lexicalisation [97].

We can also refer to a KG as a graph enhanced with representations of schema (i.e., meta-graph), identity, and ontologies [97]. A semantic schema can define the meaning of high-level terms used in the graph determining the vocabulary, or terminology, of the KG. We may also wish to define the semantics of edge labels adding properties, whereas the semantics of terms used in a graph can be defined in much more depth by ontologies (see Section 2.2). KGs are often obtained through the integration of several sources, and as a result, can be highly diverse in structure and granularity. Effective methods for extraction, enrichment, quality assessment, and refinement are required for a KG to grow and improve over time [97].

KGs have several applications in various fields, including education, scientific research, social media, and medical care. Starting from 2012, major companies, such as Google, Yahoo, Microsoft, and Facebook, have created their own KGs that power semantic searches and enable smarter processing and delivery of data [170]. In this chapter, we will focus on biological and biomedical KG construction (see Section 2.3) and ap-

plication (see Section 2.4), exploiting the concepts that biological systems are naturally represented as networks (e.g., protein-protein interaction, cells, and disease networks), and a huge amount of biomedical data is currently produced by the research community.

2.2 Ontologies in biomedical applications

Born as the branch of metaphysics dealing with “the nature of being”, ontology is a philosophical concept and discipline that deals with how to represent and categorize entities addressing questions like “how entities are grouped into categories” and “how categories are related to each other”. Ontologies classify and model hierarchical knowledge of categories, and associate a formal conceptualization to a given domain [223]. Ontologies in computer science are extensively adopted in a wide range of domains and applications, and provide machine-processable “semantics” (i.e., meaning of terms can be devised and inferred through algorithms) built on top of knowledge representation [188], therefore allowing knowledge analysis and sharing. The semantics of data can be represented with different strengths that range from simple sets of controlled terms that can be used to categorize the concepts contained in a source, to more solid representations. For example, through thesauri, terms that are synonyms can be used for representing the same real-world entity or the same relationship. These terms can be also organized in a taxonomy and thus introduce a generalization of the concepts and thus be able to more precisely describe a real-world situation. The representation with the highest level of representation is the use of ontologies that can represent the different relationships that exist among the concepts and exploit IRIs for uniquely identifying single entities. Fig. 2.1 shows the spectrum of semantic expressivity for knowledge management.

From a structural point of view, ontologies are semantic structures composed by a controlled (i.e., defined, maintained, and supervised by groups of experts) terminology and a semantic network. A controlled terminology is a collection of precise and universally comprehensible terms that univocally define and identify different concepts [162]. Terminologies that deal with molecular biology and biomedicine domains (i.e., bio-terminologies) have to cover an increasing number of terms, trying to enhance them with biological information and meaning. Examples of bio-terminologies concern biochemical and metabolic pathways (KEGG [123]), Protein families and domains (Pfam [194]), genetic diseases (OMIM [87]), Biological Processes (BP), Molecular Functions (MF), and Cellular Components (CC), the last three being the semantic components of the Gene Ontology (GO [6], see also Table 2.1). One of the major underlying challenges of data integration is curating terms, whose annotation can be human curated, assigned by experts, or in a computationally/automatically predicted way with or without human

Figure 2.1: The spectrum of semantic expressivity for knowledge management [211].

supervision. Representing a concept deals with continuous data integration and collaborative curation. Furthermore, terms can be associated to persistent identifiers, names, definitions, synonyms, reference databases, and relationships. An easy-to-use online collaborative solution for subject matter experts to map reported terms to preferred ontology (or code list) terms and facilitate ontology evolution was proposed in [200].

Several kinds of relationships can be used in an Ontology and the most common are: *IS_A*, representing the inheritance relationship, and *PART_OF*, representing instances of a class that are components of a composite object (e.g., *chromosome* is *PART_OF intracellular* in GO). Other commonly used relations in omics terminologies are *EXPRESSES*, *REGULATES*, *CONTRIBUTES_TO*, *ASSOCIATED_WITH*, *TREATS*, and *CAUSES* [162]. These relations connect biological and biomedical entities in machine-processable networks. For instance, a protein-coding gene *EXPRESSES* a protein that *REGULATES* a specific pathway. Moreover, certain proteins can contribute to or cause (*CONTRIBUTES_TO* and *CAUSES*) the development of diseases *ASSOCIATED_WITH* well-known biological processes. Finally, a drug that *TREATS* a disease can be defined by this semantics. Inverse relations can be also defined (e.g. *EXPRESSED_BY*, *REGULATED_BY*, *TREATED_BY*, and *CAUSED_BY*).

Fig. 2.2 depicts a simple bio-ontology, whose schema has been generated using Arrows [115]. Nodes represent entities and uni- and bidirectional edges represent relations. MEFG8 is a protein encoded by a gene with Entrez ID 1954 which is associated with Carpenter syndrome. GFI1B is a transcriptional repressor of MEFG8 gene.

Figure 2.2: A simple bio-ontology. Abbreviation: TR – Transcriptional Repressor.

The semantic network of an ontology can follow a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) structure like in the GO and the BTO [82], in which a node (term) can have many parent nodes (terms) connected by oriented edges without cycles. AmiGO [41] is free open source software developed and maintained by the GO Consortium which displays the GO's terms lineage in a tree browser, allowing users to view and explore the areas of the ontology graph surrounding the term.

The huge growth in online biomedical data sets such as genomics (genetic sequences, SNPs), gene expression microarrays, proteomics (mass spectrometry, protein arrays), and tissue arrays data sets raises the need for the scientific community to make sense of massive amount of data relating and building reasoning on top of them, therefore enabling mapping and interoperability of sparse and heterogeneous information, data summarization, and statistical analysis and data mining throughout bio-terminologies and bio-ontologies that can be processed by machines. This permits information management and analysis with data mining of controlled annotations to highlight most relevant biological features, help unveiling knowledge from data (e.g., identification and grouping of “similar” bio-sequences), and support translational research to quickly bring in the clinical practice new structured organization of advanced biomolecular knowledge enabling scientists to access, review, and integrate disparate knowledge resources [162].

To face fragmentation (i.e., uncoordinated bio-ontologies developed by different groups and consortia), integration, quality, and overlapping of contents issues, the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) offers the ontology Lookup Service (OLS [117]). OLS is a repository for biomedical ontologies that aims to provide a single point of access to the latest Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies (OBO [111]) together with textual search tools in bio-vocabularies and visualization of the semantic network connecting the retrieved terms. Existing OBO ontologies are undergoing coordinated reform, and new ontologies are being created on the basis of an evolving set of shared principles governing ontology development. The result is an expanding family of ontologies designed to be interoperable and logically well formed that incorporate accurate representations of biological reality [225]. Moreover, considering recent developments in the semantic web technologies, many bio-ontologies have been created by means of object-based database models and NoSQL database tools. One good example is BioPortal [249], a web portal and repository that currently provides access to 1,037 ontologies, developed by the National Center for Biomedical Ontology (NCBO). Its Web services enable a uniform mechanism to access ontologies from a variety of knowledge representation formats, such as OBO format and the W3C Web Ontology Language (OWL [180]).

OWL is a computational logic-based language defining knowledge in a computer-readable way. OWL facilitates ontologies to be translated into axioms compatible with a formalism called Description Logics, a subset of First Order Logic where the semantics of the language can be supported in a correct and complete manner using algorithms or reasoners [95]. OWL ontologies can be published in the World Wide Web and may refer to or be referred from other OWL ontologies since OWL supports “RDF-based Semantics”. RDF triples can be serialized in different ways and one of the most used is N-Triples [18] which enables more precise recording of the mapping in a machine-processable form since triples are stored as *subject predicate object* .. Syntax allows specification of URIs between “<” and “>”, whereas strings are indicated between “””. Listing 2.1 reports an example of an one-edged graph in N-Triples format, that specifies “The thesis RNA-KG is titled Construction of a KG for RNA drug analysis”. It is recommended, but not required, that N-Triples content is stored in files with an “.nt” suffix.

```
<http://example.org/thesis/RNA-KG> <http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/title> "Construction_of_a_KG_for_RNA_drug_analysis" .
```

Listing 2.1: Example of a line in N-Triples format.

RDF data can be queried by using SPARQL language [193]. SPARQL contains capabilities for querying required and optional graph patterns along with their conjunctions and disjunctions. The results of SPARQL queries can be results sets or RDF graphs.

Listing 2.2 shows an example of a SPARQL query to find the title of the thesis from the data graph in Listing 2.1. The query consists of two parts: the `SELECT` clause identifies the variables to appear in the query results, and the `WHERE` clause provides the basic graph pattern to match against the data graph.

```
SELECT ?title
WHERE
{
  <http://example.org/thesis/RNA-KG> <http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/title> ?title .
}
```

Listing 2.2: Example of a SPARQL query.

Several standard bio-ontologies can be used for the characterization of RNA molecules (see Section 1.1.2) and their interaction with other biomedical entities. Table 2.1 reports some examples of bio-ontologies that we have considered for the construction of RNA-KG. Moreover, data formats from biomedical knowledge bases (e.g., Panther [168], Reactome [80] or WikiPathways [160]) can be used for semantically annotating the RNA molecules. Please note that the National Library of Medicine’s controlled vocabulary thesaurus, named Medical Subject Headings (MeSH [208]), is a controlled vocabulary enhanced with the *IS_A* relationships.

In general, a well-recognized and globally accepted ontology for the representation of any kind of ncRNA molecules is still lacking. Often for referring to lncRNA (see Section 1.2.5) molecules, the name of the gene encoding the physically closest protein is used. Moreover, lncRNA genes with no known function are named pragmatically based on their genomic context; if there is a proximal (genomically adjacent close in physical proximity) protein coding gene (PCG) then the lncRNA genes are given a gene symbol beginning with the PCG symbol [251]. The identification scheme which is mainly used for miRNA is borrowed from miRBase [135]. This makes all the other data sources associated with miRNAs, miRBase “compliant”. Furthermore, the identification scheme associated with miRNAs is partially included in NCRO, which includes miRNA transcripts from *Homo Sapiens* cells [100].

Name	Abbr.	Description
Gene Ontology [6]	GO	GO provides the terms representing attributes of gene products in all organisms. GO covers three domains: cellular component, molecular function, and biological process.
Disease Ontology [219]	DO	DO provides the terms representing human diseases.
Monarch Merged Disease Ontology [240]	Mondo	Mondo provides the terms representing human diseases.
Human Phenotype Ontology [206]	HPO	HPO provides the terms related to medically relevant phenotypes and disease-phenotype annotations.
Vaccine Ontology [89]	VO	VO provides the terms in the domain of vaccine and vaccination.
Uber-anatomy Ontology [172]	Uberon	Uberon provides the terms that represents body parts, organs and tissues in a variety of animal species, with a focus on vertebrates.
Cell Line Ontology [214]	CLO	CLO provides the terms for representing publicly available cell lines.
Protein Ontology [174]	PRO	PRO provides the terms that represents protein-related entities (including specific modified forms, orthologous isoforms, and protein complexes).
Non-Coding RNA Ontology [100]	NCRO	NCRO provides the terms representing non-coding RNA molecules both of biological origin, and engineered.
RNA Ontology [14]	RNAO	RNAO provides the terms to capture all aspects of RNA, from primary sequence to alignments, secondary and tertiary structure, and from base pairing and base stacking interactions to sophisticated motifs.
Pathway Ontology [187]	PW	PW provides the terms for annotating gene products to pathways.
Relations Ontology [224]	RO	RO is a collection of OWL relations (<i>ObjectProperties</i>) intended for use across a wide variety of biological ontologies.
Ontology for Biomedical Investigations [10]	OBI	OBI provides the terms representing biological and clinical investigations.
Single-Nucleotide Polymorphism Ontology [71]	SNPO	SNPO provides the terms representing formal and unambiguous representation of genomic variations.
EMBRACE Data And Methods [109]	EDAM	EDAM provides the terms representing concepts that are prevalent within bioscientific data analysis, data management in life sciences.
Sequence Ontology [70]	SO	SO provides the terms representing features and properties of nucleic acid used in biological sequence annotation.
BRENDA Tissue Ontology [82]	BTO	BTO provides the terms representing anatomical structure, tissues, cell lines, cell types, and cell cultures.
Experimental Factor Ontology [158]	EFO	EFO provides the terms representing experimental variables. It combines parts of several biological ontologies, e.g., UBERON anatomy, ChEBI, and CLO.
Ontology for MIRNA Target [101]	OMIT	OMIT provides the terms to establish data exchange standards and common data elements in the microRNA (see Section 1.2.7) domain.
Ontology of Coronavirus Infectious Disease [90]	CIDO	CIDO provides the terms representing various coronavirus infectious diseases, including their etiology, transmission, pathogenesis, diagnosis, prevention, and treatment.
Medical Subject Headings [208]	MeSH	MeSH provides the terms used for indexing PubMed citations.

Table 2.1: Main bio-ontologies dealing with RNA relationships with biological molecules or biomedical entities (e.g., disease, gene, phenotype). Note that most of them are OBO ontologies. *Name* column refers to the “Ontology Homepage” according to OLS (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols>), whereas their specifications (i.e., *Description* column) are reported in OLS and BioPortal (<https://bioportal.bioontology.org>).

2.3 KG construction

Several approaches can be exploited for the representation of different real-life problems and their integration can arise several issues [35]. Nodes can be joined as a series of edges (property graphs), as a series of edges in relation to existing ontologies (RDF graphs), and the use of formal semantics with or without existing ontologies can be addressed. Constructing a KG means pre-processing (i.e., filtering and mapping among identifiers) data from several data sources to incorporate them into a common model.

The data integration issue is a well-known problem in the area of data management and many approaches have been devised to deal with relational data [86]. However, the explosion of data formats (like CSV, JSON, XML) and the variability in the representation of the same types of information [167] has pushed the need to exploit ontologies as global common models both for accessing (OBDA – Ontology-Based Data Access) and integrating (OBDI – Ontology-Based Data Integration) data sources [192]. In OBDA, queries are expressed in terms of an ontology, and the mappings between the ontology and the data sources' schema are described in the form of declarative rules.

Two approaches are usually proposed to enable data access and integration: *materialization*, where data are converted from the local data format according to the ontology concepts and relationships (i.e., data are converted into an RDF KG and locally stored in a data-warehouse of triples that can be queried through SPARQL); *virtualization*, where the transformation is executed on the fly during the evaluation of queries by exploiting the mapping rules and the ontology. In this case, only the data from the original sources involved in the query are accessed. Materialization can provide fast and accurate access to data because already organized in a centralized repository. However, data freshness can be compromised when data sources frequently change. On the other hand, virtualization allows access to fresh data but requires the application of transformations during query evaluation and can cause delay.

Many approaches are available for the specification of mapping rules like R2RML [62] (a W3C standard for relational to RDF mapping), and RML [66] that extends the standard for dealing with other formats. Moreover, SPARQL-Generate [141], YARRRML [93] and ShExML [78] were also proposed for dealing with data heterogeneity. Moreover, a fully automated Python 3 [239] Library named PheKnowLator (Phenotype Knowledge Translator) was proposed in [37] for the construction of semantically rich, large-scale biomedical KGs that are Semantic Web compliant and amenable to automatic OWL reasoning, conform to contemporary property graph standards.

In the remainder of the section we present and detail the characteristics of R2RML and PheKnowLator that we will use for RNA-KG.

2.3.1 R2RML mapping

R2RML is a language for expressing customized mappings from relational databases to RDF datasets. Such mappings provide the ability to view existing relational data in the RDF data model, expressed in a structure and target vocabulary of the mapping author's choice. R2RML mappings are themselves RDF graphs and written down in Turtle syntax [17]. Turtle is an extension of N-Triples that abbreviates URIs by using *@prefix* directive that allows declaring a short prefix name for a long prefix of repeated URIs. Listing 2.3 reports the N-Triples graph presented in Listing 2.1 converted to Turtle format. Tools like EasyRdf [104] enables automatic translation from N-Triples to Turtle formats and vice versa.

```
@prefix elem: <http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/> .
@prefix thesis: <http://example.org/thesis/> .

thesis:RNA-KG elem:title "Construction_of_a_KG_for_RNA_drug_analysis" .
```

Listing 2.3: N-Triples graph in Listing 2.1 converted to Turtle format.

R2RML enables different types of mapping implementations. Processors can offer a virtual SPARQL endpoint over the mapped relational data, or generate RDF dumps, or offer a Linked Data interface [62]. Listing 2.4 reports an example of R2RML mapping (whose input are Table 2.2a and Table 2.2b, and output is reported in Listing 2.5).

```
@prefix rr: <http://www.w3.org/ns/r2rml#>.
@prefix ex: <http://example.com/ns#>.
<#TriplesMap1>
  rr:logicalTable [ rr:tableName "UNIMI" ];
  rr:subjectMap [
    rr:template "http://data.example.com/student/{MATR}";
    rr:class ex:Student;
  ];
  rr:predicateObjectMap [
    rr:predicate ex:name;
    rr:objectMap [ rr:column "NAME" ];
  ].
<#TriplesMap2>
  rr:logicalTable [ rr:tableName "DEPT" ];
  rr:subjectMap [
    rr:template "http://data.example.com/department/{DEPTNO}";
    rr:class ex:Department;
  ];
  rr:predicateObjectMap [
    rr:predicate ex:name;
    rr:objectMap [ rr:column "DNAME" ];
  ];
  rr:predicateObjectMap [
    rr:predicate ex:location;
    rr:objectMap [ rr:column "LOC" ];
  ].
```

Listing 2.4: Example of R2RML mapping.

MATR	NAME	DEPTNO
985888	Emanuele	10

(a) UNIMI CSV.

DEPTNO	DNAME	LOC
10	Computer science	Milano

(b) DEPT CSV.

Table 2.2: UNIMI and DEPT CSV input files.

```

<http://data.example.com/student/985888> rdf:type ex:Student.
<http://data.example.com/student/985888> ex:name "Emanuele".
<http://data.example.com/department/10> rdf:type ex:Department.
<http://data.example.com/department/10> ex:name "Computer_science".
<http://data.example.com/department/10> ex:location "Milano".

```

Listing 2.5: R2RML mapping output of Listing 2.4.

A join condition *rr:joinCondition* is represented by a resource that has exactly one value for each of the following two properties [62]:

- *rr:child*, whose value is known as the join condition's child reference and must be a logical reference that exists in the logical source of the triples map that contains the referencing object map.
- *rr:parent*, whose value is known as the join condition's parent source and must be a logical reference that exists in the logical source of the referencing object map's parent triples map.

The joint query is used when generating RDF triples from referencing object maps. The example in Listing 2.6 shows a referencing object map as part of a predicate-object map. To complete the mapping document, the *ex:department* triples need to be generated. Their subjects come from the first triples map (*<#TriplesMap1>*), the objects come from the second triples map (*<#TriplesMap2>*). The output is reported in Listing 2.7.

```

<#TriplesMap1>
  rr:predicateObjectMap [
    rr:predicate ex:department;
    rr:objectMap [
      rr:parentTriplesMap <#TriplesMap2>;
      rr:joinCondition [
        rr:child "DNAME";
        rr:parent "DEPTNO";
      ];
    ];
  ].

```

Listing 2.6: Example of R2RML mapping using *rr:joinCondition*.

```
<http://data.example.com/matr/985888> ex:department "Computer_science".
```

Listing 2.7: R2RML mapping output of Listing 2.6.

A KG can be generated by semantifying and integrating heterogeneous data into an RDF data model; different tools and approaches can be applied for this purpose. In order to provide a flexible and transparent transformation, declarative mapping languages are proposed to map the data into the concepts of the unified schema or the ontology and transfer them into RDF [106]. SDM-RDFizer (RDFizer [106]) implements novel algorithms to interpret and execute the logical operators between mappings in RML, allowing thus to scale up to complex scenarios where data is not only broad but has a high-duplication rate. RDFizer is able to process data from heterogeneous data sources (CSV, JSON, RDB, and XML) by means of a set of RML rules (TriplesMap) in a multi-thread procedure, allowing the transformation of (un)structured data into an RDF KG.

Preliminary “RDFized” RNA-KG

RDFizer has been used for constructing simplified version of RNA-KG. Code can be found at the following link: https://github.com/emanuelecavalleri/testRNA-KG/tree/main/RDFizer_comparison.

Fig. 2.3 presents the preliminary RNA-KG schema. RDFizer has been used for the generation of a preliminary RNA-centered KG that involves “gene-disease”, “gene-miRNA”, and “miRNA-disease” directed relations. “gene-disease” relations are provided by Human Disease Molecular Mechanisms (HDMM [37]) KG, “gene-miRNA” by TarBase [126] (we selected 50k random rows to reduce input size), and “miRNA-disease” by miR2-Disease [113]. More details on how these data sources are structured can be found in Chapter 3.

The construction of this KG does not integrate but is compliant with the following bio-ontologies: Mondo Merged Disease Ontology (Mondo [240]), Non-Coding RNA Ontology (NCRO [100]), and Relations Ontology (RO [224]). Specifically, RO terms have been exploited to specify edges labels as in the final complete version of RNA-KG. To achieve this task, we need to map objects identifiers in RDF triples by means of RDFizer.

To construct this preliminary RNA-KG by means of RDFizer, we just need to run the one-liner in Listing 2.8 directly from command line. If you wish to run it from a Python 3 Notebook, just insert a “!” without adding any whitespace before this sentence in the desired cell.

```
python3 -m rdfizer -c config.ini
```

Listing 2.8: Command line to construct a KG using RDFizer.

Figure 2.3: Preliminary RNA-KG schema.

“config.ini” is a configuration file whose specifications are reported in Listing 2.9. RD-Fizer takes it as input to specify the KG name, store the output in the desired directory, and retrieve mapping datasets. Mappings are specified by a turtle file named “mapping.ttl”. In Listing 2.10, we provide a snippet of this file, reporting the “miRNA-gene” relations and the mapping needed to achieve this task. miRBase miRNA identifiers are mapped to NCRO terms using PheKnowLator facilities (see Section 2.3.2), and miRNA objects (whose class is *SO_0000276*, *miRNA*) put into relations with genes (specified as Entrez Gene identifiers, and whose class is *SO_0000704*, *gene*) through *RO_0002434* RO term, *interacts with*. “mapping.ttl” content can be copy-pasted in RDF Grapher [149] tool to be graphically visualized (output details of interest can be zoomed at the following link: <https://user-images.githubusercontent.com/33032169/229295644-f50cdc40-f13b-4d45-8f81-9f7fde625ffb.png>).

Subgraphs of interest can be retrieved from the preliminary RNA-KG. To accomplish this task, we developed a specific script, here commented in Listing 2.11, that exploits pickle [239], networkx [85], rdflib [30], and typing [239] Python 3 Libraries facilities. In this script, we focus our attention on *MEGF8* gene relations. Six out of twelve outgoing edges of the obtained subgraph are depicted in Fig. 2.4. We can notice *MEGF8* (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/1954>) gene *interacts with* (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002434) miRNA (whose terms are borrowed from NCRO), and *causes or contributes to condition* (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0003302) *Carpenter syndrome* (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/MONDO_0013998). *MEGF8* gene has type (www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type) *gene* (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/SO_0000704).

```

[default]
main_directory: .
[datasets]
number_of_datasets: 1
output_folder: ${default:main_directory}/output
remove_duplicate: no
all_in_one_file: no
name:RNA-KG
enrichment: yes
ordered: yes
output_format: turtle
[dataset1]
name: RNA-KG
mapping: ${default:main_directory}/mapping.ttl

```

Listing 2.9: “config.ini” file contains information to generate a preliminary version of RNA-KG and store it in the current directory.

```

@prefix rr: <http://www.w3.org/ns/r2rml#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix rml: <http://semweb.mmlab.be/ns/rml#> .
@prefix ql: <http://semweb.mmlab.be/ns/ql#> .
@prefix obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> .
<gene-miRNA>
  a rr:TriplesMap;
  rml:logicalSource [
    rml:source "./files/gene-miRNA.csv";
    rml:referenceFormulation ql:CSV ];
  rr:subjectMap [
    rr:template "http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/{gene}";
    rr:class obo:SO_0000704; ];
  rr:predicateObjectMap [
    rr:predicate obo:RO_0002434;
    rr:objectMap [
      rr:parentTriplesMap <mirbase-ncro-map>;
      rr:joinCondition [
        rr:child "mirna";
        rr:parent "mirbase"; ];
    ];
  ].
<mirbase-ncro-map>
  a rr:TriplesMap;
  rml:logicalSource [
    rml:source "./files/MIRBASE_ID_NCRO_MAP.csv";
    rml:referenceFormulation ql:CSV ];
  rr:subjectMap [
    rr:template "http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/{ncro}";
    rr:class obo:SO_0000276;
  ].

```

Listing 2.10: Snippet of “mapping.ttl” for mapping miRBase miRNA identifiers to NCRO terms, and putting miRNA objects into relations with genes through “RO_0002434” RO term, *interacts with*.

```

1 from rdflib.extras.external_graph_libs import *
2 from rdflib import Graph, Namespace, URIRef, BNode, Literal
3 import pickle
4 import networkx as nx
5 from typing import List, Set, Union
6
7 # Read in the RNA-KG generated using RDFizer
8 g = Graph()
9 g.parse("output/RNA-KG.ttl", format='ttl')
10
11 # Utility function to add edges to a graph
12 def adds_edges_to_graph(graph: Graph, edge_list: Union[List, Set],
13                       progress_bar: bool = True) -> Graph:
14
15     edge_list_updated = set(edge_list) if isinstance(edge_list, List) else edge_list
16     edge_set = edge_list_updated if progress_bar else edge_list_updated
17     for edge in edge_set: graph.add(edge)
18
19     return graph
20
21 filtered_triples = []
22 for s, p, o in g:
23     if str(s).startswith(str(URIRef('http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/1954'))):
24         filtered_triples += [(s, p, o)]
25
26 sub_graph = adds_edges_to_graph(Graph(), filtered_triples)
27 sub_graph.serialize(destination='output/subRNA-KG.nt', format='nt', encoding='utf-8')

```

Listing 2.11: Python 3 chunk to extract a subgraph of interest. In this example, we focus onto MEGF8 gene (Entrez Gene ID: 1954) relations.

Figure 2.4: MEGF8 gene relationships are retrieved from the preliminary RNA-KG and visualized by RDF Grapher [149]. Six out of twelve outgoing edges are here reported.

2.3.2 PheKnowLator

PheKnowLator poster is depicted in Fig. 2.5. The library offers tools to download, transform and/or pre-processing resources (i.e., filter data, map identifiers, and merge ontologies) into edge lists, construct KGs, and generate a wide-range of outputs.

Figure 2.5: PheKnowLator ecosystem.

PheKnowLator converts edge lists into a rich OWL-based semantic representation adding edges to the core set of ontologies, and implements a tool named OWL-NETS [36] that losslessly compresses a rich OWL-based representation into RDF. To construct RNA-KG by merging and putting into relation experimental data and ontologies, we exploited functionalities and facilities provided by the PheKnowLator ecosystem. PheKnowLator requires three dependencies documents within the resources directory to run successfully: *resource_info.txt*, *ontology_source_list.txt*, and *edge_source_list.txt*. Moreover, PheKnowLator ecosystem provides *RELATIONS_LABELS.txt* and *INVERSE_RELATIONS.txt* files that have to be downloaded.

In the remainder of this section, we explain how rows need to be stored in these textual files taking as example the KG schema depicted in Fig. 2.3. This building can be found at: <https://github.com/emanuelecavalleri/testRNA-KG>. Integrated ontologies are Mondo, NCRO, and RO. Further details on this topic can be found at the following links: <https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/wiki/Dependencies>.

Resource information

resource_info.txt is used as the master organizer for all project resources; the information is stored as a “|” delimited file. To better understand its content, we can inspect the row:

```
gene-miRNA|;;|entity-class|RO_0002434|
http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/|http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/|t|0;2|
0:./resources/processed_data/ENSEMBL_GENE_ENTREZ_GENE_MAP.txt;
1:./resources/processed_data/hsa_NCRO_Map.txt|None|None
```

This row (stored in *resource_info.txt* without any whitespace) is used for generating “gene-miRNA” edges.

- *miRNA-gene* cell corresponds to the “edge_type”, which is a string label for an edge between two nodes (*miRNA* and *gene*, the two nodes are separated by “-”). The label matches what is used in the *edge_source_list.txt* and *ontology_source_list.txt* files.
- *;;* cell is a “;”-separated string where the first item is the final prefix for the subject node and the second is the final prefix for the object node. All prefixes should be the preferred prefix from the BioRegistry (e.g., CHEBI_, GO_, and rs). Substrings before specific characters can be removed by adding the specified character, e.g., *;;GO_* means remove all characters before “:” and place GO_ instead (GO:0070888 becomes GO_0070888).
- *entity-class* cell represents how *miRNA* and *gene* terms, respectively, are represented (the two nodes are separated by “-”). The option *entity* specifies that node

identifiers (as stored in *edge_source_list.txt*) are not mapped to a specific ontology. To address this issue, PheKnowLator ecosystem includes a pickled dictionary (named *subclass_construction_map.pkl*) where the keys are node identifiers (non-ontology node data), and the values are lists of ontology class identifiers to which non-ontology node data are grounded. An example of dictionary entry is:

```
'1954': ['SO_0001217']
```

since the gene *1954* (whose human-readable identifier is “MEGF8”) “IS_A” “protein coding gene” (“protein coding gene” term is represented as *SO_0001217* in the SO). If a map between an edge term and an ontology is present (i.e., a term as specified in the *edge_source_list.txt* file is present in an ontology as in *ontology_source_list.txt*), the option *class* has to be selected. For example, “hsa-mir-605” is mapped to NCRO term *NCRO_0002939*.

- *RO_0011002* is a term belonging to the RO whose human-readable label is “regulates activity of”. RO terms are used to connect two nodes (*miRNA* and *gene*) establishing an edge between them, guaranteeing common semantics.
- *t* cell corresponds to the delimiter, a character used to split input text rows into columns (e.g., *t* for tab-delimited data or , for comma-delimited data). In this specific case, “miRNA-gene” edges, as retrieved by the ecosystem from *edge_source_list.txt*, are delimited by tabs (i.e., “miRNA-gene” edges are stored as a TSV file named as specified in *edge_source_list.txt*).
- *0;2* specifies the two-column indices to retrieve *gene* and *miRNA* instances, respectively, from the TSV file as specified in *edge_source_list.txt* (i.e., *gene* instances are stored in the zeroth column, and *miRNA* instances are stored in the second column of the input data source).
- <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/> and <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> cells correspond to eventual prefixes to generate a correct URI; the first item is the prefix for the subject node (*gene*) and the second is the final prefix for the object node (*miRNA*). These cells allow the instantiation of Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) as node identifiers (e.g., <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/1954> and http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCRO_0002939).
- *0:./resources/processed_data/ENSEMBL_GENE_ENTREZ_GENE_MAP.txt;1:./resources/processed_data/hsa_NCRO_Map.txt;* cell is used for mapping identifiers from different data sources: a string of mapping information for each node in an edge is needed (“;” is used to separate the two strings, and can be empty if no mapping is required). In our example, the first node (*gene*) requires data from the

zeroth column in the *ENSEMBL_GENE_ENTREZ_GENE_MAP.txt* file, and translates Ensembl identifiers (e.g., “ENSG00000010404”) to Entrez gene identifiers (e.g., “5389”). The second node (*miRNA*) requires data contained in the first column of the mapping file *hsa_NCRO_Map.txt*, and translates miRNA identifiers from miRNA sequence identifiers (e.g., “hsa-mir-665”) to NCRO terms (e.g., “NCRO_0002939”).

- Last two cells are left empty in this example (*None*). They are related to evidence criteria filtering (i.e., select rows with associated scores above a certain cut-off) and filtering criteria that can be used to filter an input data source (e.g., select rows related only to pre-defined human proteins). Multiple filtering sets can be passed, where each set is separated by “:”. An unrelated example is `6;=;Homo sapiens::5;.startswith('protein');`, meaning: “select only rows equal to string *Homo sapiens* from column 6 and (: selects only rows starting with – *.startswith()* Python 3 method – the word *protein* from column 5)”.

Ontology source list

ontology_source.list.txt is used to identify and download specific ontologies. To better understand its content, we can inspect the row:

```
disease, resources/ontologies/mondo_with_imports.owl
```

- *disease* is a human readable identifier for the subsequently specified ontology.
- *resources/ontologies/mondo_with_imports.owl* specifies the location PheKnowLator ecosystem needs to retrieve the associated ontology (in this example, Mondo Disease Ontology).

Edge source list

edge_source.list.txt is used to identify specific publicly available data sources that will be used to derive edges between ontology classes and instances of ontology classes. To better understand its content, we can inspect the row:

```
gene-miRNA, resources/edge_data/gene-miRNA.txt
```

- *gene-miRNA* specifies the specific edge as in *resource_info.txt*.
- *resources/edge_data/gene-miRNA.txt* specifies the location PheKnowLator ecosystem needs to retrieve the associated edge list.

Relations labels

PheKnowLator ecosystem provides you all possible relations in the RO. Relations identifiers and associated human-readable labels are extracted and stored in the *RELA-*

TIONS_LABELS.txt file running the chunk of Python 3 code reported in Listing 2.12. To better understand the content of this textual file, we can inspect the row:

RO_0002434 interacts with

- *RO_0002434* specifies the term in the RO.
- *interacts with* specifies the human readable label associated with *RO_0002434* in the RO.

```
1 # download ontology
2 if not os.path.exists(unprocessed_data_location + 'ro_with_imports.owl'):
3     command = '{ } --merge-import-closure -o { }'
4     os.system(command.format(owltools_location, 'http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ro.owl',
5                             unprocessed_data_location + 'ro_with_imports.owl'))
6
7 # load graph
8 ro_graph = Graph().parse(unprocessed_data_location + 'ro_with_imports.owl')
9
10 results = {str(x[2]).lower(): str(x[0]) for x in ro_graph
11            if '/RO_' in str(x[0]) and 'label' in str(x[1]).lower()}
12
13 # write data to file
14 with open(relations_data_location + 'RELATIONS_LABELS.txt', 'w') as outfile:
15     outfile.write('Label' + '\t' + 'Relation' + '\n')
16     for k, v in results.items():
17         outfile.write(str(v).split('/')[ -1] + '\t' + str(k) + '\n')
```

Listing 2.12: Generation and storage of relations labels in the RO.

Inverse relations

RO terms often appear with *owl:inverseOf* properties that prove useful for identifying inverse relations. Syntactically, *owl:inverseOf* is a built-in OWL property with *owl:ObjectProperty* as its domain and range. An axiom of the form P1 *owl:inverseOf* P2 asserts that for every pair (x,y) in the property extension of P1, there is a pair (y,x) in the property extension of P2, and vice versa. Thus, *owl:inverseOf* is a symmetric property [16]. An example is reported in Listing 2.13: *hasChild* is an *owl:inverseOf hasParent*.

```
<owl:ObjectProperty rdf:ID="hasChild">
  <owl:inverseOf rdf:resource="#hasParent"/>
</owl:ObjectProperty>
```

Listing 2.13: Example of *owl:inverseOf*.

To store inverse relations in “INVERSE_RELATIONS.txt” file, PheKnowLator ecosystem follows the approach proposed in Listing 2.14. To make it easier to look up the inverse relations, each pair is listed twice, e.g., *location of owl:inverseOf located in* and *located in owl:inverseOf location of*.

```

1 # identify inverse relations
2 with open(relations_data_location + 'INVERSE_RELATIONS.txt', 'w') as outfile:
3     outfile.write('Relation' + '\t' + 'Inverse_Relation' + '\n')
4     # s=subject, p=predicate, o=object
5     for s, p, o in ro_graph:
6         if 'owl#inverseOf' in str(p):
7             if 'RO' in str(s) and 'RO' in str(o):
8                 outfile.write(str(s.split('/')[ -1]) + '\t' + str(o.split('/')[ -1]) + '\n')
9                 outfile.write(str(o.split('/')[ -1]) + '\t' + str(s.split('/')[ -1]) + '\n')

```

Listing 2.14: Generation and storage of inverse relations present in the RO.

Ontologies processing

Ontologies are downloaded and imported by means of *download_ontology* method, reported in Listing 2.15. Ontologies are then merged and cleaned by running Python notebook https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/notebooks/Ontology_Cleaning.ipynb as it is.

```

1 def download_ontology(ontology):
2     if not os.path.exists(ontology_data_location + ontology + '_with_imports.owl'):
3         command = '{} {} --merge-import-closure -o {}'.format(
4             owltools_location,
5             'http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/' + ontology + '.owl',
6             ontology_data_location + ontology + '_with_imports.owl')

```

Listing 2.15: Method for downloading ontologies.

2.3.3 Edge dataset construction

Edge dataset is built by downloading, processing, filtering, merging, and cleaning data from public RNA-based data sources; an example of how this occurs is presented in Listing 2.16.

```

1 data_downloader('https://dianalab.e-ce.uth.gr/downloads/tarbase_v8_data.tar.gz',
2                 unprocessed_data_location)
3
4 with tarfile.TarFile(unprocessed_data_location + 'tarbase_v8_data.tar', 'r') as tar_ref:
5     tar_ref.extractall(unprocessed_data_location)
6
7 gene_miRNA = pd.read_csv(unprocessed_data_location + 'TarBase_v8_download.txt', sep='\t',
8                          dtype={"cell_line": "string"})
9
10 # For the time being, we keep only Homo sapiens rows
11 gene_miRNA = gene_miRNA[gene_miRNA['species'].str.contains("Homo sapiens")]
12
13 gene_miRNA['geneId'] = gene_miRNA['geneId'].str.replace("\(hsa\)", '')
14 gene_miRNA['geneName'] = gene_miRNA['geneName'].str.replace("\(hsa\)", '')
15
16 gene_miRNA.to_csv(edge_data_location + 'gene-miRNA.txt', header=None, sep='\t', index=None)

```

Listing 2.16: Python script for adding gene-miRNA edges from TarBase to RNA-KG.

Mappings

Besides the Ensemble-Entrez mapping already provided by PheKnowLator ecosystem (*ENSEMBL_GENE_ENTREZ_GENE_MAP.txt*), new mappings have been added for this building. Disease description to DO identifiers mapping is provided by miR2Disease [113] at the following link <http://watson.compbio.iupui.edu:8080/miR2Disease/download/diseaseList.txt>. DO terms can be easily be mapped to Mondo ones by using “gets_ontology_class_dbxrefs” method provided by PheKnowLator ecosystem. A new method called “gets_ontology_class_labels” (see Listing 2.17) has been developed for extracting NCRO-miRBase mapping.

```
1 # Get ontology classes' label
2 def gets_ontology_class_labels(graph: Graph) -> Tuple:
3     dbx_uris: Dict = dict()
4     dbx = [x for x in graph if 'label' in str(x[1]).lower() if isinstance(x[0], URIRef)]
5     for x in dbx:
6         if str(x[2]).lower() in dbx_uris.keys(): dbx_uris[str(x[2]).lower()].append(str(x
7             [0]))
8         else: dbx_uris[str(x[2]).lower()] = [str(x[0])]
9     dbx_type = {str(x[2]).lower(): 'DbXref' for x in dbx}
10
11     ex_uris: Dict = dict()
12     ex = [x for x in graph if 'exactmatch' in str(x[1]).lower() if isinstance(x[0], URIRef)]
13     for x in ex:
14         if str(x[2]).lower() in ex_uris.keys(): ex_uris[str(x[2]).lower()].append(str(x[0]
15             ))
16         else: ex_uris[str(x[2]).lower()] = [str(x[0])]
17     ex_type = {str(x[2]).lower(): 'ExactMatch' for x in ex}
18
19     return {**dbx_uris, **ex_uris}, {**dbx_type, **ex_type}
20
21     ncro_label = gets_ontology_class_labels(ncro_graph)[0]
22
23     ncro_dict = {str(k): {str(i).split('/')[1] for i in v} for k, v in ncro_label.items()}
24
25     with open(unprocessed_data_location + 'hsa_NCRO_Map.txt', 'w') as outfile:
26         for k, v in {**ncro_dict}.items():
27             outfile.write(str(k) + '\t' + str(v).replace('{', '').replace('\n', ''))
28                 + '\n')
29
30 # hsa_NCRO_Map.txt.txt stores rows as: hsa-mir-605 NCRO_0002939
```

Listing 2.17: Method for getting ontology classes labels applied to NCRO terms.

Metadata

KGs in PheKnowLator can be built with or without the inclusion of node and relation metadata (i.e. labels, descriptions or definitions, and synonyms).

A variety of metadata are pulled from the data sources that are used to support external edges added to enhance the core set of ontologies. The code snippet in Listing 2.18 is meant to provide a snapshot of how data are organized in the metadata dictionary

`node_metadata_dict.pkl`. There are three high-level keys.

- “Nodes”: every node has a *Label*, *Description*, *Synonym*, and *Dbxref* (whenever possible).
- “Edges”: edges are keyed by a label that represents the edge type (the same label that is used in `resource_info.txt` and `edge_source_list.txt` files). Metadata that are obtained from specific sources that are not ontologies are added as a nested dictionary keyed by the filename.
- “Relations”: relations or “owl:ObjectProperty” objects are similar to nodes, every relation has a *Label*, *Description*, and *Synonym* (whenever possible).

```
1 {
2   'nodes': {
3     '1954': {
4       'Label': 'MEGF8',
5       'Description': "The protein encoded by this gene is a single-pass type I
6         membrane protein of unknown function
7         that contains several EGF-like domains, Kelch repeats, and PSI domains.
8         Defects in this gene are a cause of Carpenter syndrome 2.
9         Two transcript variants encoding different isoforms have been found for
10        this gene. [provided by RefSeq, Dec 2012]",
11       'Synonym': 'SBP1|CRPT2|EGFL4|C19orf49',
12       'Dbxref': 'HGNC:3233|Ensembl:ENSG00000105429|
13         MIM:604267|AllianceGenome:HGNC:3233', ... }, ... },
14     'NCRO_0002815': {
15       'Label': 'hsa-mir-342',
16       'Description': "This miRNA sequence is 21
17         nucleotides long and is found in Homo sapiens.",
18       'Synonym': 'Homo Sapiens miRNA 342|mir-342',
19       'Dbxref': 'MalaCards:MIR342|LncBase:hsa-miR-342|
20         ENA:LM380355.1:1..21:ncRNA', ... },
21   'edges': {
22     'gene-miRNA': {
23       'http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCRO_0002815-
24         https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/1954': {
25         'gene-miRNA.txt': {
26           'Evidence': [{'Interaction': '[MEGF8 gene transcripts are targeted
27             and upregulated by hsa-miR-342] in cancer/malignant cells.'},
28           'InteractionActions': 'affects^upregulation|affects^oncogenesis',
29           'PubMedIDs': '20374639'}]}}, ... }, ... }, ... },
30   'relations': {
31     'RO_0002434': {
32       'Label': 'interacts with',
33       'Description': 'A relationship that holds between
34         two entities in which the processes executed
35         by the two entities are causally connected.',
36       'Synonym': 'in pairwise interaction with'}, ... }
37 }
```

Listing 2.18: Snippet of “`node_metadata_dict.pkl`”.

KG construction

The PheKnowLator KG build algorithm has been designed to run from three different stages of development: “full” (runs the full KG build, except graph closure), “partial” (runs the build algorithm up through merging ontologies adding edge data, which excludes closure, the removal of metadata, and the creation of edge lists), and “post-closure” (searches for a closed KG .owl file and then performs the steps to remove owl semantics metadata and create edge lists). RNA-KG has been built by means of the “full” approach. Once dependencies documents have been prepared, input data (including non-ontology ones) and ontologies downloaded and processed, KG relations handled, a preliminary version of RNA-KG can be generated. The code snippet in Listing 2.19 is meant to provide a snapshot of how RNA-KG can be build.

In PheKnowLator ecosystem, new data can be added to the KG using two different construction approaches: “instance-based” or “subclass-based”. If “instance-based” construction approach has been chosen, each new edge is added as an instance of an existing class (via *rdf:Type*); whereas if “subclass-based” construction approach has been selected, each new edge is added as a subclass of an existing ontology class (via *rdfs:subClassOf*). Further details on this topic can be found at the following link: https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/resources/construction_approach/README.md#knowledge-graph-construction-approaches. The current version of RNA-KG exploits an “instance-based” approach by setting parameter *construction='instance'* in *FullBuild* constructor (see Listing 2.19).

KG OWL semantics is filtered by means of OWL-NETS [36] (whose facilities are implemented in PheKnowLator ecosystem) by setting parameter *decode_owl='yes'* in *FullBuild* constructor (see Listing 2.19).

```
1 # specify input arguments to construct kg instance
2 kg = FullBuild(construction='instance',
3               node_data='no', # we will not add metadata in this building
4               inverse_relations='yes',
5               decode_owl='yes',
6               cpus=psutil.cpu_count(logical=True),
7               write_location='./resources/knowledge_graphs'
8               )
9
10 kg.construct_knowledge_graph()
```

Listing 2.19: Snippet for constructing RNA-KG.

2.4 Application of KG in biomedical applications

A biomedical KG contains different types of nodes, relationships, and basic properties representing the underlying biological and biomedical knowledge in a flexible data model. This model should be easy to interpretate, update, and improve. Thus, this enables collecting, structuring and integrating knowledge, and the use of powerful algorithms for different kinds of applications. Several are the purposes of predicting algorithms: predicting treatments for and causes of different diseases [8, 203], building pharmacovigilance and drug safety surveillance systems [27, 120], identifying comorbid diseases [3, 26], and prioritizing novel disease targets to predict previously unknown drug-disease associations or repurpose drug candidates [36]. Furthermore, biomedical KGs allow the construction of interactive tools to help users with different expertizes interact with complex data [40, 220]. Biological and biomedical KGs capture knowledge and represent a map of how individual components relate to each other in an ideal abstraction allowing us to make sense of this complexity with a view to produce predictive statements and hypotheses (e.g., causal relationships and correlations) that can be experimentally validated, keeping in mind that the vast majority of human diseases are the consequence of multiple molecular alterations and genetic interactions.

An approach for integrating different biological data into a biological KG was proposed in [263]. The approach designs a Connecting Ontology *CO* to integrate all the external ontologies describing the involved data sources. By exploiting algorithms for fusing and integrating annotations, an enriched KG is obtained that spans multiple data sources and is annotated by the integrated biological ontology. The effectiveness of this approach is shown by integrating *rice gene-phenotype* and *Lactobacillus* data sources by gluing together the GO, Trait, Disease, and Plant Ontologies.

The Precision Medicine KG (named PrimeKG [46]) was developed to represent holistic and multimodal views of diseases. PrimeKG integrates more than 20 high-quality resources with more than 4 million relations that capture information like disease-associated perturbations in the proteome, biological processes, and molecular pathways.

A virtualization approach based on an ontology-based federation of three data sources (Bgee, OMA, and UNIProtKB) was presented in [222]. Starting from a semantic model for gene expression named GenEx, the authors propose using mapping rules for dealing with the different formats of the three sources and allow the issue of joint queries across the sources by exploiting SPARQL endpoints.

Another approach for integrating different biological data related to COVID-19 disease into a biological KG was proposed in [122]. CovidKG.ORG is an online, interactive,

Figure 2.6: The meta-graph (i.e., schema) of the heterogeneous biomedical KG used in [94]. Nodes (circles) represent entities and edges represent unidirectional and bidirectional relations.

trust-worthy COVID-19 Web-scale KG stored in a scalable sharded MongoDB storage. CovidKG.ORG hosts several advanced search engines (over paper titles, abstracts, captions, and publication fields) and use the extracted information to conduct enrichment analysis.

A KG designed for Project Rephetio, which aims to systematically identify why drugs work and predict new therapies for drugs, is Hetionet [94]. Fig. 2.6 illustrates the connectivity between different types of biomedical nodes (e.g., genes, compounds, and diseases) and edges in Hetionet. Notice that multiple types of edges can connect the same two nodes. For example, a compound can have a relationship to a gene by binding its protein and/or by up-regulating it. Since the biological effects of these two mechanisms are very different, they are given separate representations in the network.

Scalable Precision Medicine Open Knowledge Engine (SPOKE [176]) is designed to connect basic molecular data from heterogeneous data sources, with clinical insights and environmental exposures. In [212], an open-source platform designed for integrating omics data into the clinical decision-making process has been proposed. Clinical

Knowledge Graph (CKG) combines experimental data, public databases, bio-ontologies and the literature.

The Monarch Knowledge Graph [221] is part of a large system designed and maintained by the Monarch Initiative with the goal of representing gene-phenotype relationships across multiple model organisms. The Monarch platform [165] is used to construct this KG, considering several different bio-ontologies which can be integrated with each other. The Knowledge Base of Biomedicine (KaBOB [152]) is a large-scale semantically rich representation of important biomedical concepts and their relationships. KaBOB is grounded in OBO ontologies and represents data for seven model organisms.

Finally, a Human Disease Molecular Mechanisms (HDMM [37]) KG was developed by using the PheKnowLator ecosystem. HDMM's schema has 18 primary node types and 35 primary edge types; its knowledge was obtained by combining data from 12 OBO ontologies and 31 Linked Open Data.

2.4.1 Biomedical KG evaluation, challenges, and open issues

Evaluating a biomedical KG includes verifying its formal semantics, data quality, and potentiality to infer new biologically meaningful edges among nodes. However, the variety of data sources and formats (e.g., gene expression, RNA-Seq, proteomics, metabolomics, and SNPs data), the huge size of data that are produced, the heterogeneity of data sources, and the different semantics that can be adopted, make this activity challenging and time/resource consuming. To validate a biomedical KG, the following metrics can be adopted: percentage of triples (randomly sampled) consistent with a real-life fact as judged by domain experts [75], accuracy, timeliness, trustworthiness, consistency, completeness, and availability [244], precision and recall when predicting specific edge types, and computational performance [35]. On the other hand, existing inference methods scale poorly and are constrained in their ability to harness large knowledge-bases by the extremely large computational loads involved [37], making human curated validation necessary.

Chapter 3

RNA-based Data Sources

In order to construct RNA-KG, we examined public online repositories for non-coding RNA sequences and drugs (as described in Section 1.1.2) that include annotations and interactions among RNAs, between RNAs and other different types of molecules (e.g., protein), and between RNAs and other biomedical entities (e.g., disease). An extensive literature review was carried out to identify repositories developed by well-reputed organizations and published in top journals of the sector. Only recent repositories that are kept updated and contain significant amounts of data have been considered.

In this chapter, we present the characteristics of the identified data sources. Specifically, we have outlined more than 50 sources that have been classified according to the RNA molecules of interest, specifying the number of species involved, the format in which data are stored, and the presence of APIs or SPARQL endpoints for accessing the data. Biological and biomedical relationships of interest have been identified in the selected sources and mapped in the standard RO Ontology. Finally, we have also identified the number of relationships that can be extracted from the considered data sources.

Efforts have also been devoted to the mapping of identifiers coming from different data sources, to the identification of properties that enhance relationships among biological entities (e.g., a ncRNA-gene relationship occurring only in a specific cell line or tissue), and to the investigation of inclusions among data sources (i.e., databases included in larger ones or relationships repeated among unrelated databanks). Identifiers have also been examined to ground underlying concepts to bio-ontologies terms to guarantee and support standard and common semantics during the construction of RNA-KG.

This chapter is organized as follows. Section 3.1 provides an overview on RNA-based

public data sources and identified relationships involving RNA molecules and other biomedical entities. Section 3.2 analyzes the different identifiers employed by RNA-based data sources, and focuses on how they can be mapped to existing well-recognized bio-ontologies (as described in Section 2.2).

3.1 Public RNA-based data sources

The analysis of the literature pointed out the availability of more than 50 public RNA-based repositories. The papers presenting these data sources were published in top journals (e.g., NAR, BMC Bioinformatics, Science, RNA Journal, and IEEE/ACM TCBB) between 2008 and 2023 but the majority were published in the last 5 years.

In the remainder of the section, we first describe the main characteristics of the analyzed data sources. Then, we describe the characteristics of the relationships that can be extracted. Finally, we point out some properties that can be extracted from the data sources and used to characterize entities and relationships.

3.1.1 Main characteristics of data sources

The main characteristics of RNA-based data sources and identified relations involving RNA molecules and other biomedical entities (e.g., protein, chemical, and disease) are reported in Tables 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3. Those tables share a common structure, and are organized according to the main type of non-coding RNA or RNA drug made available. RNA molecules are the ones considered in Chapter 1. For each repository, we report the RNA molecule of interest (**Type** column), the number of distinct sequences of this type of RNA molecules (**# RNA** column), and the considered species **Species** column (note that HS and MM tags are used when the involved species are only *Homo Sapiens* and *Mus Musculus*). Experimental data can be directly associated with *Homo Sapiens* ncRNA molecules (like tRFs in tRFdb [136], tsRFun [243], and MINTbase [191]) or to molecules of viruses and bacteria that are involved in alterations of the human phenotype (as in the case of viroidDB [140] and TBDB [159]). Moreover, they can contain information on antibacterial drug targets, such as riboswitches in the RSwitch [186] (see Table 3.3). Furthermore, we specify the number of distinct relationships with biomedical and biological entities (**In rel. with** and **# rel.** columns), the repository underlying format (**Format** column – e.g., relational database *rel*, flatfile, and website interface), and if APIs or SPARQL endpoints are present (**API** column). Note that, none of the identified databases is specific for piRNA molecules (discussed in Section 1.2.11) related to *Homo Sapiens*, although they are contained in interRNA-based data sources (i.e., database not specific for a single ncRNA molecule, analyzed in Table 3.3).

Type	DB name	Species	# RNAs	In rel. with	# rel.	Format	API
miRNA	miRBase [135]	271	38,589	(stem-loop) miRNA	48,860	rel/CSV	no
	miRDB [52]	5	7,086	mRNA	3,519,884	CSV	no
	miRNet [72]	10	7,928	SNP mRNA snoRNA chemical TF epi. mod. lncRNA pseudogene circRNA disease	67,532 3,025,487 9,738 4,935 2,282 1,955 31,345 59,417 80,4086 32,004	rel/CSV	API
	EpimiR [59]	7	617	epi. mod.	1,974	CSV	no
	HMDD [103]	HS	1,206	disease	35,547	CSV	no
	miR2Disease [113]	HS	299	disease	1,939	CSV	no
	TargetScan [163]	5	5,168	mRNA	2,850,014	CSV	no
	SomamiR DB [22]	HS	1,078	mRNA circRNA lncRNA disease	2,313,416 428,237 127,025 2,424	CSV	no
	TarBase [126]	18	2,156	mRNA	665,843	rel/CSV	no
	miRTarBase [99]	28	4,630	mRNA	2,200,449	CSV	no
	SM2miR [151]	21	1,658	chemical	4,989	CSV	no
	TransmiR [235]	19	785	TF	2,433	CSV	no
	PolymiRTS [23]	HS	11,182	disease	83,516	rel/CSV	no
	dbDEMC [256]	HS	3,268	disease	160,800	CSV	no
	TAM [154]	HS	1,209	mol. function miRNA TF disease tissue	2,538 1,218 165 12,516 58	CSV	no
	PuTmiR [11]	HS	1,296	TF	12,097	CSV	no
	miRPathDB [127]	HS, MM	29,430	mol. function	3,063	CSV	no
	miRCancer [255]	HS	236	disease	878	CSV	no
	miRdSNP [34]	HS	249	disease SNP	786 758	CSV	no
	miRandola [209]	14	1,002	extracell. form chemical	3,262 25	CSV	no

Table 3.1: Main miRNA-based data sources. Abbreviations: SNP – Single Nucleotide Polymorphism; TF – Transcription Factor; epi. mod. – epigenetic modification; mol. function – molecular function; extracell. form – extracellular form.

Type	DB name	Species	# RNAs	In rel. with	# rel.	Format	API
mRNA vaccine	DrugBank [250]		4	disease	7	rel/RDF	SPARQL/API
s(i/h)RNA	ICBP siRNA [148]	HS, MM	147	mRNA	147	HTML	no
	DrugBank [250]		4	mRNA disease	3 3	rel	SPARQL/API
RNA aptamer	Apta-Index [146]		230	chemical protein	77 153	rel	no
	DrugBank [250]		2	protein disease	2 2	rel/RDF	SPARQL/API
ASO	eSkip-Finder [54]	4	2,196	mRNA	11,778	rel	no
	DrugBank [250]		12	protein mRNA disease	12 7 11	rel/RDF	SPARQL/API
gRNA	Addgene [121]	29	296	gene	321	HTML	no
lncRNA	LncBook [145]	HS	323,950	miRNA protein disease biological context	146,092,274 772,745 34,536 95,243	rel/CSV	no
	LncRNADisease [47]	4	19,166	disease	208,256	CSV	no
	LncExpDB [144]	HS	101,293	mRNA	28,443,865	rel/CSV	no
	dbEssLnc [265]	HS, MM	207	biological role biological process	207 28	JSON	no
	lncAtlas [161]	HS	6,768	cell. comp.	2,429,368	CSV	no
	NONCODE [266]	39	644,510	disease	32,226	rel	no
	Lnc2Cancer [77]	HS	3,402	disease	9,254	CSV	no
	LncRNAWiki [150]	HS	106,063	small protein disease biological context cell. comp. gene miRNA TF biological process mol. function chemical	9,387 7,634 18,453 4,969 509 210 232 10,806 1,800 789	rel/CSV	no

Table 3.2: Main mRNA vaccine-, siRNA-, shRNA-, RNA aptamer, ASO-, gRNA-, and lncRNA-based data sources. Note that **Species** column is empty for all mRNA vaccines, RNA aptamers, and for *DrugBank* entries since identified sources provides only synthetic RNA molecules. For gRNA molecules, **Species** column is referred to the Cas9-associated species. Abbreviations: cell. comp. – cellular compartment; mol. function – molecular function.

Type	DB name	Species	# RNAs	In rel. with	# rel.	Format	API
Ribozyme	Ribocentre [64]	1,195	21,084	biological process	34	rel	no
Viral RNA	ViroidDB [140]	9	9,891	ribozyme	17,460	CSV	no
Riboswitch	TBDB [159]	3,621	23,497	protein	23,535	CSV	no
	RSwitch [186]	50	215	bact. strain	215	rel/CSV	no
tRF	tRFdb [136]	7	863	tRNA	792	CSV	no
	tsRFun [243]	HS	3,940	miRNA	45,165	CSV	no
				tRNA disease	4,620		
MINTbase [191]	HS	28,824	tRNA	125,285	CSV	no	
snoRNA	snoDB [33]	HS	751	gene mRNA lncRNA miRNA pseudogene rRNA snoRNA snRNA tRNA	763 276 45 17 10 735 670 164 164	CSV	no
tRNA	tRNAdb [116]	681	9,758	amino acid	8,872	rel	no
All RNA	RNAInter [124]	156	455,887	chemical histone mod.	10,890 1,060,685	CSV	API
	RNALocate [57]	104	123,592	cell. comp.	213,429	CSV	API
	RNA Disease [49]	117	91,245	disease	343,273	CSV	API
	ncRDeathDB [252]	12	648	prog. cell death	4615	CSV	API
	cncRNADB [102]	21	2,002	anatomy	2,598	CSV	API
	ViRBase [53]	152	56,614	viral RNA	829,339	CSV	API
	Vesiclepedia [182]	41	20,490	extracell. form	388,154	CSV	no
	DirectRMDb [264]	25	19,702	epi. mod.	904,712	CSV	no
Modomics [28]	32	999	pathway	1,674	rel/RDF	API	

Table 3.3: Main ribozyme-, viral RNA-, riboswitch-, snoRNA-, tRNA-, and interRNA-based data sources. For what regards viral RNA molecules, **Species** column specifies the number of human viruses genera. Abbreviations: bact. strain – bacterial strain; histone mod. – histone modification; cell. comp. – cellular compartment; prog. cell death – programmed cell death; extracell. form – extracellular form; epi. mod. – epigenetic modification.

Figure 3.1: Available relationships involving RNA molecules and biological entities (e.g., gene, protein, and amino acid). Different colors are used to represent the different ranges of relationships, as reported in the legend in the bottom of the heatmap.

The majority of the considered data sources ($\geq 80\%$) export data in a flatfile format (CSV). Only a small fraction of them (around 20%) make available API for accessing data stored in a relational database. Only DrugBank offers an RDF data representation providing a SPARQL endpoint. Data sources classified as miRNA type are the most represented (around 35% belongs to this category). They are followed in numerosity by inter-RNA (9), and lncRNA (8) types. miRNet, LncRNAWiki, and snoDB are those that provide the most identified relationships (10, 10, and 9, respectively).

Fig. 3.1 sums up available relations involving RNA molecules and biological entities (e.g., gene, protein, and amino acid) that we have identified in the different data sources. miRNA-lncRNA interactions are the most numerous. We can retrieve around 150 million distinct relationships of this type from public RNA-based data sources. In terms of numerosity, they are followed by miRNA-mRNA interactions (around 52 million) and lncRNA-mRNA interactions (around 28 million). Around 800 thousand distinct relationships can also be identified for protein-lncRNA interactions. These categories of molecules often interact with each other in specific diseases. ASO-protein is the less represented one since it contains interactions derived from DrugBank. DrugBank ASO category contains only 12 approved or under-investigation ASO drugs.

In addition to the so far discussed data sources, RNAcentral is a collector coordinated by the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI [38]), which imports non-coding RNA sequences from multiple databases and enables integrated text search, sequence similarity search, bulk downloads, and programmatic data access through a reliable API (whose documentation is provided at the following link: <https://rnacentral.org/api>). Fig. 3.3 provides an integrated view of ncRNA sequences in RNAcentral, specifying imported data sources with their ncRNA molecule of interest. The sequences are mapped to reference genomes from more than 250 species using BLAST-Like Alignment Tool (BLAT [128]), and a genome browser is provided in order to browse all mapped sequences, view individual sequences in their genomic context, or download genome coordinates in several formats. Furthermore, RNAcentral imports modified nucleotides from Modomics and PDB [21], miRNA targets from TarBase, and GO annotations from QuickGO [24]. All sequences are annotated with Rfam [118, 119] models to provide warnings and additional information. It also provides secondary structure diagrams for a wide range of RNA types.

3.1.2 Detail on the available relationships

Starting from the exigence of understanding whether the content of the different data sources overlaps, we have examined the entities and relationships made available in the considered data sources and identified containment (or overlapping) data sources.

The result of our study is reported in Fig. 3.2. As the reader can see at first glance, TarBase, miRTarBase, miR2Disease, HMDD, SM2miR, EpimiR, TransmiR, and TAM are included in miRNet. TarBase, miRTarBase, in turn, are entirely included in RNAcentral. The under/over expressed miRNA molecules in specific diseases in the data source TAM are relationships mutated from HDMM which in turn is included in miRNet. miRandola collects the miRNA entries that are also made available in Vesciclepedia along with the relationships with circRNA and lncRNA and they intersect with miRNet. The data source NONCODE includes many other lncRNA-based data sources like LncRNADisease, Lnc2Cancer, and LncRNAWiki. NONCODE and LncBook are in their turn included in RNAcentral. RNAcentral includes miRBase, Ribocentre, tRNADB, snoDB, and Modomics too.

Addgene, RSwitch, TBDB, viroidDB, dbEssLnc, and lncATLAS are non-connected components because they provide relations not available in other databanks. An example is Addgene with the identified gRNA-gene interaction. MINTbase, tsRFun, and tRFdb share common relationships, specifically tRF-tRNA interactions. DrugBank share interactions with eSkip-Finder, Apta-Index, and ICBP siRNA (respectively, RNA aptamer-protein, ASO-mRNA, and siRNA-mRNA interactions).

Finally, we analyzed relationships among the interRNA-based sources RNAInter, RNALocate, RNADisease, ncRDeathDB, cncRNADB, and ViRBase. They are nicknamed “Sister Projects” since they are updated and maintained by the same research team. Common semantics in inter-RNA “sister databases” result useful for data handling because downloadable data share a practically identical structure. They are organized following the subsequent pattern:

[*Internal ID* | *Interactor1* | *Interactor2* | *PMID* | *Score*]

Score column refers to a metric for measuring the reliability and trustworthiness of the relationship between *Interactor1* and *Interactor2*. *PMID* is the unique identifier number used in PubMed for the article reporting the relation.

3.1.3 Node properties

During the analysis of public RNA-based repositories, additional relevant properties were identified. These attributes can be included in the representation of RNA-KG. Table 3.4 specifies the attributes that can be specified for each kind of RNA molecule whose values come from the repositories described in Section 3.1

	mRNA	sno	tRF	g	mi	si	pg	ASO	protein	rs	apt	lnc	rz	circ	viral	epiMod	dis	sm
synonym(s)	x	x			x		x					x		x			x	x
sequence	x	x	x		x			x	x	x		x	x	x	x			
gen.cont.		x	x		x							x						
category			x						x	x					x	x		
Cas9 species				x														
application				x														
plasmid ID				x														
PMID				x	x					x	x		x		x			
label	x										x		x					
evidence					x													
(inter/intra)g.					x							x						
FDA(Y/N)	x					x		x			x							
chem.mod.								x										
weight											x							
bind.temp.											x							
affinity											x							
specificity											x							
source s.					x										x			
sec.struct.									x									

Table 3.4: Main biologically relevant node properties from considered public data sources. Abbreviations: **sno** – snoRNA; **g** – gRNA; **mi** – miRNA (includes stem-loop miRNA and xeno-miRNA); **si** – siRNA; **pg** – pseudogene; **rs** – riboswitch; **apt** – aptamer; **lnc** – lncRNA; **rz** – ribozyme; **circ** – circRNA; **viral** – viral RNA; **epiMod** – epigenetic modification; **dis** – disease; **sm** – small molecule; **gen.cont.** – genomic context (specified as: chr.:x-y[+/-] – chromosome number, from position to position, + or - strand); **(inter/intra)g.** – intergenic or intragenic; **FDA(Y/N)** – FDA approved (yes/no); **chem.mod** – chemical modification(s); **source s.** – source species of an exogenous sequence (for xeno-miRNA and viral RNA species); **sec.struct.** – secondary structure.

Figure 3.3: Currently, RNAcentral is formed by 51 imported public RNA-based data sources, 8 others are being imported.

3.2 Identification of entities and relationships

During the acquisition of the RNA-based data sources, we have noted the use of different identification schemes for the local identification of biological entities. A lot of work has been done for the selection of well-accepted and recognized controlled vocabularies, thesaurus, and ontologies that can be used for a uniform representation of the entities' identifiers and their properties. However, we were forced to use locally generated identification schemes because standard ontologies for their representation are still missing. As stated in Section 2.2, the only recurrent and standard identification schema is for miRNA sequences since identifiers are always borrowed from miRBase. This makes all the other data sources associated with miRNAs miRBase "compliant". Unfortunately, grounding extracted miRNA instances to NCRO terms revealed to be a hard task because miRBase identifiers for human molecules are only partially included in NCRO. To avoid information loss, NCRO has not been integrated in the current re-

lease of RNA-KG. URLs from miRBase have been used instead. For instance, mature sequence “hsa-miR-660-3p” has been mapped to https://www.mirbase.org/cgi-bin/mature.pl?mature_acc=MIMAT0022711. Its stem-loop sequence “hsa-mir-660” has been mapped to https://www.mirbase.org/cgi-bin/mirna_entry.pl?acc=MI0003684. The translation is provided by miRBase itself at the following link: <https://www.mirbase.org/ftp/CURRENT/aliases.txt.zip>.

RNA-KG contains entities at different granularities for representing the biological characteristics of entities that are relevant for the kinds of analysis that we wish to carry out. While RNA and gene sequences do have specific identifiers and each of them is specifically represented, other biological concepts (e.g. cellular compartments) are abstractly represented by their corresponding ontological terms. For instance, to represent a “nucleus” in relation with a precise sequence (for which a specific identifier is given), we directly employ the ontological term *GO_0005634* (“nucleus”) without further specifying the nucleus of the precise cell in which the sequence may be contained or located in. A specific and precise representation for biological entities such as cellular compartments would be infeasible to represent for computational and biological reasons.

Identifiers for other entities (e.g., disease, protein, and pathway) have been manually grounded or grounded by means of PheKnowLator primitives *gets_ontology_classes*, *gets_ontology_statistics*, *gets_object_properties*, *gets_ontology_class_dbxrefs*, *gets_ontology_class_synonyms*, and *gets_ontology_definitions*. A new method to extract class labels from terms belonging to a given ontology has been developed and named *gets_class_labels* (see Sections 2.3.2 and 4.3).

Non-ontology identifiers (i.e., IDs not included in any terminology) have been manually added to PheKnowLator ecosystem dictionary *subclass_construction_map.pkl* (see Section 4.3.3). Whenever feasible, SO terms have been used for classifying non-ontology sequences, this explains why the column **SO** is frequently checked. For example, miRNA sequences have been collected under the term *SO_0000276*, whose human-readable label corresponds to *miRNA* and description is “small, ~22-nt, RNA molecule that is the endogenous transcript of a miRNA gene (or the product of other non-coding RNA genes. Micro RNAs are produced from precursor molecules (SO:0001244) that can form local hairpin structures, which ordinarily are processed (usually via the Dicer pathway) such that a single miRNA molecule accumulates from one arm of a hairpin precursor molecule. Micro RNAs may trigger the cleavage of their target molecules or act as translational repressors. [<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12592000> <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/11081512>]”.

Type	DB name	SO	Mondo	GO	ChEBI	OBI	PRO	HPO	EDAM	EFO	BTO	VO
miRNA	miRBase	x										
	miRDB	x										
	miRNet	x	x	x	x	x	x	x				
	EpimiR	x	x									
	HMDD	x	x					x				
	miR2Disease	x	x			x		x				
	TargetScan	x										
	SomamiR DB	x	x					x	x			
	TarBase	x						x		x		
	miRTarBase	x				x						
	SM2miR	x			x	x				x		
	TransmiR	x										
	PolymiRTS	x	x									
	dbDEMC	x	x						x		x	
	TAM	x		x				x				x
	PuTmiR	x		x				x				
	miRPathDB	x		x								
	miRCancer	x	x						x			
miRdSNP	x	x						x				
miRandola	x		x	x	x	x	x	x		x		
mRNA vaccine	DrugBank		x									x
siRNA	ICBP siRNA	x				x						
	DrugBank		x		x		x	x				

Table 3.5: Considered miRNA-, mRNA vaccine-, and siRNA-based data sources with adopted terminology or whose terms can be mapped to an existing terminology of a bio-ontology.

Table 2.1 shows the ontologies used for grounding RNA-KG entities and their relationships. The final product is a set of structured data (instances and relations) in the shapes defined by the schema in Chapter 4. The specification of the several standard ontologies to which considered data were grounded is reported in Tables 3.5 and 3.6. Note that we avoid to report DO and MeSH since their terms can be mapped to Mondo and ChEBI ones; the same occurs for PW and GO. In general, as already stated in Section 2.2, a semantic conceptualization has not been completely defined for the representation of ncRNA molecules. We hope our efforts towards the construction of an RNA-centered KG will set the basis for the development of a new well-defined ncRNA ontology.

Type	DB name	SO	Mondo	GO	ChEBI	OBI	PRO	HPO	EDAM	EFO	BTO	VO
RNA aptamer	Apta-Index	x			x	x						
	DrugBank	x	x				x					x
ASO	eSkip-Finder	x			x					x		
	DrugBank	x	x					x				
gRNA	Addgene	x										
lncRNA	LncBook	x			x					x		
	LncRNADisease	x	x	x		x		x	x	x	x	
	LncExpDB	x		x								
	dbEssLnc	x		x	x							
	lncATLAS	x		x						x	x	
	NONCODE	x		x								
	Lnc2Cancer	x	x	x		x						
LncRNAWiki	x	x	x	x		x						
Ribozyme	Ribocentre	x		x					x			
Viral RNA	ViroidDB	x		x					x			
Riboswitch	TBDB	x		x						x		
	RSwitch	x		x	x					x		
tRF	tRFdb	x								x		
	tsRFun	x	x					x				
	MINTbase	x										
snoRNA	snoDB	x		x							x	
tRNA	tRNAdb	x			x					x		
All RNA	RNAInter	x			x	x				x		
	RNAlocate	x		x								
	RNADisease	x	x					x				
	ncRDeathDB	x		x								
	cncRNADB	x								x		
	ViRBase	x	x							x		
	Vesiclepedia	x		x		x		x		x		
	DirectRMDb	x								x		
Modomics	x	x		x		x	x					

Table 3.6: Considered RNA aptamer-, ASO-, gRNA-, lncRNA-, ribozyme-, riboswitch-, tRF-, snoRNA-, tRNA-, and interRNA-based data sources with adopted terminology or whose terms can be mapped to an existing terminology of a bio-ontology.

Chapter 4

RNA-KG

In Chapter 3 we have identified a plethora of heterogeneous sources containing RNA molecules and different kinds of interactions. In this chapter, we wish to provide a meta-graph representing the types of molecules and relationships that exist among them. The meta-graph is a simple form of ontology that contains relationships whose meaning is clearly established. For this reason, we adopt the Relations Ontology (RO [224]) to ensure precise semantics. This ontology provides both direct and inverse relationships and they are considered to guarantee bidirectionality when needed in the knowledge graph that will be generated according to the meta-graph. However, in the considered sources there are also relationships that are not present in RO. In the chapter, we will propose the introduction of new terms for their accurate description.

Starting from the developed meta-graph and the PheKnowLator library, we will show the procedure for constructing RNA-KG and so obtaining a knowledge graph that properly integrates the different data sources in a common and uniform data model that can be exploited for conducting different kinds of analysis. At the current stage of development, RNA-KG contains more than 6 million triples containing 24 types of biological and biomedical entities and 56 kinds of relationships. Finally, we will provide some topological properties of RNA-KG computed by means of GRAPE [40] Python 3 Library.

This chapter is organized as follows. Section 4.1 analyzes relations provided by RO that are useful for RNA-KG construction, specifically for providing edge labels among biomedical entities. Section 4.2 describes the schema we defined to populate RNA-KG with instances coming from data sources discussed in Chapter 3. Section 4.3 explores scripts and required input files for constructing RNA-KG by means of PheKnowLator facilities. Finally, Section 4.4 presents the topological characteristics of RNA-KG.

4.1 Representation of relationships through RO

Data sources discussed in Chapter 3 contain different kinds of relations that can be exploited for the construction of the KG. These relationships should be mapped into RO terms for guaranteeing uniform and precise semantics. This mapping has been realized manually by studying terms' definitions to ensure a strong degree of adherence to RO semantics. We remark that the *definition* term itself is grounded to Information Artifact Ontology (IAO [45]) *IAO_0000115* term (IAO is an ontology of information entities, originally driven by work by the OBI digital entity and realizable information entity branch). According to IAO, when we manually scan RO terms definitions, we are considering the “official definition, explaining the meaning of a class or property. Shall be Aristotelian, formalized and normalized. Can be augmented with colloquial definitions”. We retain this may reduce odds of choosing a totally wrong RO term to map relations.

To make the semantics of RNA-KG compliant with HDMM (see Section 2.4), we have surveyed HDMM relations in *resource.info.txt* with the purpose of expanding as little as possible the set of relations to be used in RNA-KG. This behavior has been adopted because terms referring to relations in RO are 667 (as in term-label mappings stored in *RELATIONS.LABELS.txt*, file generated by the Python 3 script presented in Section 2.3.2, and needed by PheKnowLator ecosystem to correctly build KGs). For instance, if *protein-gobp* relation (where *gobp* is the label for GO Biological Process) in HDMM meta-graph employs the term *RO_0000056* (whose human-readable label is “participates in”), *ncRNA-gobp* (where *ncRNA* is a placeholder for a possible non-coding RNA category, e.g., miRNA) in the RNA-KG meta-graph will also exert *RO_0000056*.

Table 4.1 reports the main relations that have been identified. For each relation, we specify the RO identifier (whenever the relation is included in RO) and the corresponding label. Whenever feasible, we have used bidirectional relations (e.g., *interacts with*), and introduced the inverse relations only in case of an available unidirectional relation (e.g., *develops from* and *develops into*). In the following, we explain the reasons for choosing the RO terms for describing the interactions identified in the data sources.

- The relation *interacts with*, available in RO with the meaning “a relationship that holds between two entities in which the processes executed by the two entities are causally connected”, has been employed to represent general interactions between biological entities.
- *molecularly interacts with* substitutes *interacts with* for representing two nodes that are molecular entities directly and physically interacting with each other (e.g., via a stable binding interaction or a brief interaction during which one modifies

the other). This relation is used to represent specific interaction processes at molecular levels (e.g., complementary base pairing occurring in RNAi in miRNA-mRNA interaction or tRNA molecule charged with a specific amino acid).

- *regulates activity of (RO_0011002)* term definition is “the entity A has an activity that regulates the activity of the entity B. For example, A and B are gene products where the catalytic activity of A regulates the kinase activity of B” and has been used, e.g., for miRNA-mRNA interactions. Its two-term leaves *involved in positive regulation of (RO_0002429)* and *involved in negative regulation of (RO_0002430)* further specify if the process is a positive or negative regulation. In RO semantic network structure, these two terms are bidirectionally connected via *is negative form of* and *is positive form of* edges.
- To connect ncRNA with biological roles, it sounded spontaneous to employ the term *has biological role (RO_0002260)*. “Biological role” semantics is defined by *CHEBI_24432* term, that specifies a “role played by the molecular entity or part thereof within a biological context”. Examples are lncRNA-biological role interactions from dbEssLnc. *gene product of (RO_0002204)* term definition tells us that “x has gene product of y if and only if y is a gene (SO:0000704) that participates in some gene expression process (GO:0010467) where the output of that process is either y or something that is ribosomally translated from x”. For ncRNA, it has proved useful in the specification of small protein products of lncRNAs. Moreover, *gene product of editor note* specifies “we would like to be able to express the rule: if t transcribed from g, and t is a noncoding RNA and has an evolved function, then t has gene product g”. Being this note related to an RNA context, RO updates for *gene product of* term will be addressed. The exact reverse definition (“x has gene product y if and only if x is a gene (SO:0000704) that participates in some gene expression process (GO:0010467) where the output of that process is either y or something that is ribosomally translated from y”) is applied to *has gene product* term (*RO_0002205*).
- For ncRNA relations directly involving the underlying nucleotide sequence, it turned useful considering *overlaps sequence of*, *is upstream sequence of*, and *is downstream sequence of* (respectively identified by *RO_0002526*, *RO_0002528*, and *RO_0002528*). Sequence overlapping (“x overlaps the sequence of x if and only if x has a subsequence z and z is a subsequence of y”) has proved useful for representing viral RNA-ribozyme interactions, whereas *is upstream sequence of* and *is downstream sequence of* terms have been mainly employed for representing riboswitch-(tRNA) protein interactions provided by TBDB.

- *develops from* (RO_0002202) and *develops into* (RO_00022023) terms have been added to RNA-KG edge set to represent processes that make an entity evolve (e.g., stem-loop miRNA evolving into mature miRNA sequences).
- As in HDMM, *causally influences* (RO_0002566) and *causally influenced by* (RO_0002559) terms have been considered for relations having SNP as one of the two endpoints. One of *causally influences* child nodes is *decreases by repression quantity of* (RO_0011007). This term has been employed, for example, if a certain ncRNA decreases by repression the quantity of a specific gene product.
- With the aim of guaranteeing compatibility with HDMM, *ncRNA-gomf* (gomf stands for GO Molecular Function) relations have been labeled with *has function* (RO_0000085). Similarly, *function of* term (RO_0000079) labels gomf-ncRNA edges. Cellular compartments or tissues that express specific ncRNA have been put into connection with those ncRNAs by virtue of *expresses* RO_0002292. On the other hand, those same ncRNA molecules are *expressed in* RO_0002206 those cellular compartments or tissues. For representing the over-expression of a ncRNA relative to some background (as in case-control studies), *over-expressed in* (RO_0002245) has been included in RNA-KG.
- To represent relations between ncRNA that resemble or are related to each other sufficiently to warrant a comparison (e.g., two identical miRNA molecules except for a single nucleotide) we have considered *in similarity relationship with* (RO_HOM0000000). Similar ncRNA molecules (mainly miRNAs) or ncRNAs co-involved specific biological pathways can also be clustered. A 1-to-many relation between a ncRNA cluster and clustered ncRNA molecules has been labelled via *results in assembly of* (RO_0002588) term.
- As discussed in Chapter 1, RNA molecules can also serve as carriers for other bio-active molecules or be carried by, e.g., transporter proteins, lipoproteins or lipid nanoparticles (as with liposomes in mRNA vaccines). As in HDMM, these two relations are represented, respectively, through *is carrier of* (RO_0010002) and *generically depends on* (RO_0010001) terms. Biological molecules that instead contain ncRNAs have been connected with them using *contains* (RO_0001019) term. Molecular containers could include exosomes, membrane vesicles, spherical vesicles made of ionizable lipids, microparticles, and microvesicles. The same ncRNA molecules are *contained in* (RO_0001018) specific molecular containers.
- Biological processes and pathways have been connected with ncRNA molecules by means of *participates in* (RO_0000056). Vice versa, the opposite relation (biological pathway-ncRNA) has been labeled with *has participant* (RO_0000057).

- “Disease” is the last entity we want to connect ncRNA sequences. ncRNAs are known to be involved in the development of specific diseases. If the data source specifies that a certain ncRNA has some causal role for the considered disease, *causes condition* (RO_0003303) has been employed. If also a contributing role that influences the condition may be present, the parent term *causes or contributes condition* (RO_0003302) has been addressed. On the opposite, ncRNA sequences could also become drugs to treat genetic disorders or, more in general, diseases. ncRNA drug-disease interactions have been labeled with *is substance that treats* (RO_0002606) term. This term perfectly suits this task since its definition is “c is a substance that treats d if c is a material entity (such as a small molecule or compound) and d is a pathological process, phenotype or disease, and c is capable of some activity that negative regulates or decreases the magnitude of d”. For the inverse relation disease-ncRNA drug, its RO inverse term *is treated by substance* (RO_0002302) term has been addressed.

In some situations, the RO terms do not properly represent the relationships identified in the data sources. In these cases, RO needs to be extended to properly represent the relationships occurring in the data sources.

- The relations *hyper-* and *hypomethylated in* are useful in describing different methylation states of RNA molecules (mainly lncRNA) in different types of disease.
- Even though *mutualistically regulates* can be closely approximated by *regulates activity of*, it introduces the concept of mutuality necessary for the relation to exist and happen.
- *bonded with high affinity and specificity with* is specifically intended for representing situations, such as aptamer-protein binding, in which high affinity and specificity between involved molecules are needed.
- *silences* can be thought of as an extension of the already existing *decreases by repression quantity of*, adding the specification of complete knockdown of the gene product, e.g., due to complementary pairing with a ncRNA (mainly siRNA).
- *hosts* relation is specifically intended for gene-snoRNA interactions since gene transcription (according to the Central Dogma of Molecular Biology, see Section 1.1) is a process that can be regulated by specific snoRNA molecules.
- *charges* instead is specifically intended for aminoacyl-tRNA complexes (see Section 1.2.2) since it allows the representation of chemical bonds established between tRNA molecules and cognate amino acid residues through the

formation of ester bonds by aminoacyl-tRNA synthetases (this mechanism is named “charging” [259]).

- Finally, we noticed that RO misses a specific relation directly involving human pathogens (e.g., gram-positive and -negative bacteria or viruses). Therefore, we introduced the *capable of inhibiting pathogen* relation, suitable, e.g., for representing inhibition of specific bacterial strains by riboswitch molecules.

In Table 4.1, *Approximated by* column has been introduced to specify the most similar RO term with respect to newly introduced relations. Concepts specified by relations belonging to the extended set can be thought as proper subset-inclusions of RO approximations. Employing RO terminology instead of the proposed extension for RNA-KG, does gain semantic compatibility with RO and HDMM, but the trade off is the loss of precise specification power of the relations (i.e., if one chooses to build RNA-KG employing only RO terms, specificity and edge details introduced by new relations are lost).

Identification of inverse relations allows the construction of a bidirectional RNA-KG, ensuring precise semantics guaranteed by RO. Table 4.2 reports all the terms discussed in Table 4.1 for which an inverse is already present in RO. RO inverse relations have been identified using the *owl:inverseOf* property and stored in “INVERSE_RELATIONS.txt” by means of PheKnowLator ecosystem as described in Section 2.3.2. Since *owl:inverseOf* properties are bidirectional, we avoid duplicating entries.

During the analysis of public RNA-based repositories, additional relevant edge properties were identified. As with node attributes in Section 3.1.3, this would prove relevant to improve RNA-KG. In Table 4.3, we specify whether an edge (labeled with RO terms) can be enhanced with additional properties, whose instances come from the sources described in Chapter 3. We avoid reporting inverse properties for ease of visualization since they share the same properties of their inverse edges. Attributes have been identified for RO terms (table header reports digits after the last “0” in the identifier) and for *mutualistically regulates* (whose column is named **m.reg.** for the sake of conciseness).

Relation ID	Name	Approximated by
RO:0002429	involved in positive regulation of	
RO:0002430	involved in negative regulation of	
RO:0002434	interacts with	
RO:0002436	molecularly interacts with	
RO:0002260	has biological role	
RO:0002204	gene product of	
RO:0002205	has gene product	
RO:0002526	overlaps sequence of	
RO:0002528	is upstream sequence of	
RO:0002529	is downstream of sequence of	
RO:0002202	develops from	
RO:0002203	develops into	
RO:0002566	causally influences	
RO:0002559	causally influenced by	
RO:0011002	regulates activity of	
RO:0000085	has function	
RO:0000079	function of	
RO:0002245	over-expressed in	
RO:HOM0000000	in similarity relationship with	
RO:0002588	results in assembly of	
RO:0003302	causes or contributes to condition	
RO:0003303	causes condition	
RO:0011007	decreases by repression quantity of	
RO:0010002	is carrier of	
RO:0010001	generically depends on	
RO:0002606	is substance that treats	
RO:0002302	is treated by substance	
RO:0000056	participates in	
RO:0000057	has participant	
RO:0002292	expresses	
RO:0002206	expressed in	
RO:0001018	contained in	
RO:0001019	contains	
	hypermethylated in	RO:0003302
	hypomethylated in	RO:0003302
	mutualistically regulates	RO:0011002
	bonded with high affinity and specificity with	RO:0002436
	silences	RO:0011007
	hosts	RO:0002434
	charges	RO:0002436
	capable of inhibiting pathogen	RO:0002434

Table 4.1: Main relations among bio-entities in RNA-KG.

Relation ID	Name	Inverse R. ID	Inverse Name
RO:0002528	is upstream sequence of	RO:0002529	is downstream sequence of
RO:0002292	expresses	RO:0002206	expressed in
RO:0001019	contains	RO:0001018	contained in
RO:0000056	participates in	RO:0000057	has participant
RO:0002204	gene product of	RO:0000057	has gene product
RO:0002606	is substance that treats	RO:0002302	is treated by substance
RO:0002202	develops into	RO:0002203	develops from
RO:0002566	causally influences	RO:0002559	causally influenced by
RO:0000085	has function	RO:0000079	function of
RO:0010002	is carrier of	RO:0010001	generically depends on

Table 4.2: Relations among bio-entities in RNA-KG from which an RO inverse exists, and has been introduced in RNA-KG.

	2528	2292	1019	56	2204	11002	2430	3302	2429	2428	2434	m.reg.
p-value	x							x				
gen.cont.	x											
expr.value		x										x
e.method		x	x		x		x	x			x	
label		x	x	x			x	x			x	x
tissue		x		x			x					
PMID		x		x			x	x				x
sample			x	x				x				
cell line		x										x
mod.res.				x								
MoA				x				x				
SNP						x	x	x	x	x	x	
condition							x				x	x
(in)direct reg.							x					
NCBI probe									x	x		
% mRNA KD									x	x		
% protein KD									x	x		
epi.mod.												x

Table 4.3: Main biologically relevant edge properties from selected sources. Abbreviations: **gen.cont.** – genomic context (specified as: chr.:x-y[+/-] – chromosome number, from position to position, + or - strand); **expr.value** – expression value; **e.method** – evidence method; **mod.res.** – modified residue(s); (in)direct reg. – direct or indirect regulation; **KD** – KnockDown; **epi.mod.** – epigenetic modification.

4.2 A meta-graph representing RNA-KG relationships

Relations in Table 4.1 along with their inverse in Table 4.2 and sequences of bio-molecules have been used for the generation of a meta-graph, here reported in Fig. 4.1a (this meta-graph includes only relations belonging to or approximated with RO). The meta-graph sets the basis for the construction of RNA-KG, i.e., the meta-graph here presented constitutes the schema of RNA-KG. To simplify the visualization of the meta-graph we omitted most of the non-RNA bio-molecular and medical entities that are known to play an important role to study the biology and support the discovery of novel RNA drugs, and also edges retrieved from interRNA data sources (see Table 3.3). Indeed, the meta-graph in Fig. 4.1a can be further extended with other nodes representing other biological entities (e.g., diseases, epigenetic modifications, small molecules, tissues, biological pathways, and cellular compartments) and relevant relations included in RNA-KG. In Fig. 4.3, we propose the identified extended schema. Furthermore, the meta-graph points out the presence of a central hub, named “GENE/mRNA”, bound to many kinds of ncRNA nodes; this topological feature might have a deep impact on the discovery of new unconsidered interactions among ncRNA molecules.

Gene and mRNA are distinguished biological entities (mRNA molecules are only one of the possible transcriptional products of genes, and a gene can be related to many transcripts, see Section 1.1.2 and specifically Fig. 1.6), and ncRNAs often interact with mRNAs and not directly at a genetic level. However, Gene and mRNA entities are merged together in the current version of RNA-KG meta-graph, which leads to an incorrect approximation from a biological point of view. This strong assumption stems from the fact that data sources listed in Chapter 3 generally do not provide the specific transcript a ncRNA bonds with. This results in mRNA molecules named after the gene they are transcribed from.

RNA-KG meta-graph can be compared to the analogous graph (see Fig. 4.1b) obtained from the literature review about RNA molecules carried out in Chapter 1. We can outline the presence of disconnected components, in particular involving “piRNA”, “riboswitch”, “viral RNA”, and “circRNA” nodes. The differences between nodes and edges between these meta-graphs are depicted in Fig. 4.3. Green nodes and edges represent entities and relations present in selected sources but not observed in literature whereas red nodes and edges represent entities and relations present in literature, but not in the sources. We can note that disconnected components (except for node “piRNA” because, as stated in Chapter 3, none of the considered sources reported piRNA molecules for *Homo Sapiens*) disappeared in RNA-KG meta-graph and that, even if we are dealing more or less with the same nodes, edges cardinality consistently augmented.

(a) RNA-KG meta-graph.

(b) "Literature-based" RNA-centered meta-graph.

Figure 4.1: RNA-centered meta-graphs.

Figure 4.3: RNA-KG meta-graph including all biomedical entities and relations among them.

As presented in Section 2.4, HDMM is a biomedical KG that models and incorporates existing knowledge of molecular mechanisms from ontologies, publicly available data, and the literature to construct an unbiased KG. During its construction, knowledge quality was ensured by a PhD-level biologist. HDMM has been built by means of PheKnowLator ecosystem facilities and therefore proves easy to be merged to RNA-KG.

In Fig. 4.4, we depict RNA-KG schema integrated with HDMM one (edges in violet are those belonging to HDMM). Fig. 4.4 is not intended to be analyzed in its single details, it is only meant to be a demonstration of how RNA-KG can be extended with new entities and relations, and how powerful KGs are in collecting different relations coming from the most diverse data sources in the biomedical field. RNA-KG can be seen as the first step toward a large KG that involves other types of molecules and biomedical entities with the ultimate goal of developing new drugs not only based on RNA. Finally, merging RNA-KG to HDMM and, in general, to any other valiant biomedical KG, highlights different components/views of interest that can be extracted.

4.3 RNA-KG implementation

RNA-based data and bio-ontologies discussed in Chapter 3 are downloaded, processed, mapped, and cleaned by means of PheKnowLator facilities in order to build edges converging in RNA-KG. Moreover, we focus on describing input files and dependencies needed by PheKnowLator ecosystem to efficiently compile. The current release of RNA-KG has been built and constantly maintained. Code for building RNA-KG is available at the following link: <https://github.com/AnacletoLAB/RNA-KG>.

The current version of RNA-KG, whose SPARQL endpoint is available and can be queried at the following link: <http://fieval.anacleto.di.unimi.it:10035/#/repositories/RNA-KG>. This release does not exploit metadata.

4.3.1 Edge dataset

The current RNA-KG meta-graph considers 56 relations (78 including inverse ones) involving 24 biological or biomedical entities that have been identified from 25 out of 54 selected public data sources. Interoperability issues related to the use of different identifiers by these databanks have been addressed by grounding instances to terminologies from eight well-accepted and standardized ontologies in the biomedical domain (RO, Mondo, ChEBI, PRO, GO, SO, VO and PW ontologies). Entities are mRNA, gene, miRNA, disease, tRF, snoRNA, viral RNA, biological process, cellular component, biological role, lncRNA, snRNA, circRNA, protein, chemical, gRNA, ASO, siRNA, shRNA, aptamer, mRNA vaccine, riboswitch, biological processes, and ribozyme. Their

instances have been retrieved from HDMM, TarBase, miR2Disease, tsRFun, snoDB, LncRNADisease, LncBook, dbEssLnc, lncATLAS, ncRDeathDB, miRNet, SM2miR, Ad-gene, DrugBank (mRNA vaccine, aptamer, ASO, and siRNA data have been considered), MIT/ICBP siRNA Database, LncExpDB, TBDB, Ribocentre, ViroidDB, Vesciclepedia, miRandola, and SomamiR DB.

Starting from these concepts, the following relationships have been identified among them (from the different considered data sources):

- All HDMM data (edges already provided by PheKnowLator ecosystem) can be downloaded from the PheKnowLator GCS Bucket, which is organized by release and build. RNA-KG currently includes “gene-disease”, “gene-gene”, “chemical-gene”, “chemical-disease”, “protein-protein”, “gene-protein”, “chemical-protein”, “chemical-pathway”, “chemical-biological process”, “gene-pathway”, “protein-pathway”, “protein-biological process”, “pathway-cellular component”, “chemical-cellular component”, and “protein-cellular component” interactions from HDMM. Data for these interactions are retrieved from sources considered gold standards in their field such as DisGenNet [189], The Comparative Toxicogenomics Database (CTD [63]), GeneMANIA [245], STRING [230], Reactome [80], UniProt [15], and GO annotation files (GAF). Selected columns and rows in RNA-KG are the same of HDMM. These interactions are respectively mapped via *RO_0003302* (“causes or contributes to condition”), *RO_0002435* (“genetically interacts with”), *RO_0002434* (“interacts with”), *RO_0002606* (“is substance that treats”), *RO_0002436* (“molecularly interacts with”), *RO_0002205* (“has gene product”), *RO_0002434*, *RO_0000056* (“participates in”), *RO_0002436*, *RO_0000056*, *RO_0000056*, *RO_0000056*, *RO_0000056*, *RO_0000056*, *RO_0002180* (“has component”), *RO_0002436*, and *RO_0001025* (“located in”) terms. Entrez Gene IDs have been used for representing genes, Mondo terms for diseases, ChEBI for chemicals, PRO for proteins, PW for pathways, and GO for cellular components and biological processes.
- “miRNA-gene” edges from TarBase are filtered according to species. Only *Homo Sapiens* rows for columns specifying gene identifiers and miRNA sequences are considered for RNA-KG construction. miRBase identifiers for mature and stem-loop sequences are used in RNA-KG for identifying miRNA molecules, whereas Entrez IDs are employed for genes as in HDMM. *RO_0011002* (“regulates activity of”) have been used for ground interactions to RO terminology.
- “miRNA-disease” relations from miR2Disease consider only human disease, so data are downloaded and kept as they are. Diseases have been grounded to Mondo terms. As with entities causing or contributing to disease development in

HDMM, we employed *RO_0003302* (“causes or contributes to condition”) relation for representing “ncRNA-disease” interactions.

- “tRF-miRNA” relations from tsRFun are considered only if the corresponding False Discovery Rate (FDR, computed according to Benjamini–Hochberg procedure) is lower than 0.01. This FDR threshold ensures only a small proportion of false positives among data. Generic *RO_0002434* (“interacts with”) has been used for representing this interaction.
- “tRF-disease” relations from tsRFun are considered only if the absolute value of the \log_2 Fold Change ($|\log_2 FC|$) is greater or equal to 1. Thresholds over 1 and under -1 of the $|\log_2 FC|$ corresponds to a gene expression that is doubled or halved in the considered pathological condition, ensuring a strong correlation between the two entities. Only cancers are provided, so we have grounded cancer types to Mondo terms.
- snoDB provides many relationships involving human snoRNA molecules that can be easily integrated into RNA-KG. “snoRNA-gene”, “snoRNA-miRNA”, “snoRNA-snoRNA”, “snoRNA-lncRNA”, and “snoRNA-snRNA” interactions have been selected by considering the two columns with the molecular entities of interest from the CSV file. The only issue was “exploding” rows since multiple values are stored as semicolon-separated values in the same cell (e.g., row “snoRNA x” interacts with “gene y; gene z; gene w” has to be substituted with three distinct rows as follows: “snoRNA x” interacts with “gene y”, “snoRNA x” interacts with “gene z”, and “snoRNA x” interacts with “gene w”). Generic *RO_0002434* (“interacts with”) has been used for semantically annotating these interactions in RNA-KG.
- “lncRNA-disease” and “circRNA-disease” interactions from LncRNADisease have been selected according to species (only *Homo Sapiens* rows are kept in RNA-KG). lncRNA and circRNA molecules cause or contribute to disease development, so we used *RO_0003302* (“causes or contributes to condition”) term for representing this relation.
- “lncRNA-protein” relations from LncBook underwent filtering on the protein column. Only proteins with a corresponding in PRO have been considered. Generic *RO_0002434* (“interacts with”) has been used for semantically annotating these interactions in RNA-KG.
- “lncRNA-biological role” interactions from dbEssLnc contain only three types of “biological role”: general, tumor suppressor gene and oncogene. Those concepts have been added to the non-ontology dictionary via *CHEBI_24432* (“biolog-

ical role”) term, as specified by *RO_0002260* (“has biological role”) term definition (“c has-biological-role r iff c has-role r and r is a biological role (CHEBI:24432)”), used for representing this kind of interaction.

- “lncRNA-cellular compartment” interactions from lncATLAS have been grounded to *RO_0001018* (“contained in”) term. Cellular compartments have been grounded to GO Cellular Compartment terminology (e.g., “nucleus” to *GO_0005634*).
- “lncRNA-, miRNA-, and snoRNA-programmed cell death” interactions from ncR-DeathDB have been grounded to *RO_0001018* (“contained in”) term. Programmed cell death concepts have been grounded to GO Biological Process terminology (e.g., “necrosis” to *GO_0097300*).
- “protein-miRNA” from miRNet, specifically human “stem-loop miRNA-TF” interactions, have been included in the current version of RNA-KG. Being TFs proteins, they have been grounded to PRO terminology, and relations mapped to *RO_0002428* (“involved in regulation of”) term.
- “chemical-miRNA” interactions are retrieved from SM2miR. The only issue was “exploding” rows since multiple values are stored as “+”-separated values in the same cell, similarly to what occurred with snoDB data. *RO_0011002* (“regulates activity of”) has been use.
- Similarly, “circRNA-miRNA” interactions for human sequences have been retrieved from SomamiR DB cancer somatic mutations, and put into relation with *RO_0002434* (“interacts with”) term.
- From Addgene “gRNA-gene” datatable we retrieved “Plasmid ID” and “Target Gene” columns. Addgene gRNA sequences are added to non-ontology data dictionary as *SO_0000602* (“guide RNA”). Relations are represented with *RO_0011007* (“decreases by repression quantity of”) term.
- “ASO-gene”, “ASO-disease”, “ASO-protein”, “siRNA-gene”, “siRNA-disease”, “aptamer-protein”, “aptamer-disease”, and “mRNA vaccines-disease” interactions from DrugBank have been manually filtered and mapped by reading drug descriptions and targets from the considered source. All ncRNA drugs have been mapped to non-ontology data dictionary with SO terms specifying the possibility of RNA sequence being exogenous/synthetic (e.g., *SO_0000646* – “siRNA” – term defined as “small RNA molecule that is the product of a longer exogenous or endogenous dsRNA”), whereas for mRNA vaccine we decided to employ *VO_0000186* term (“RNA vaccine”). Being RNA in DrugBank RNA drugs or therapies, “RNA-disease” interactions have been mapped via *RO_0002606* (“is substance that

treats”) term. For “ncRNA-gene”, *RO_0002430* (“involved in negative regulation of”) term was used. Furthermore, “aptamer-protein” interactions are represented with *RO_0002436* (“molecularly interacts with”). Finally, “ASO-protein” interactions have been divided into *RO_0011007* (“decreases by repression quantity of”) and *RO_0010002* (“is carrier of”) relations, according to DrugBank drug descriptions.

- “siRNA- and shRNA-gene” relations from The MIT/ICBP siRNA Database have been downloaded by means of *read_html* Pandas [234] method. Validated human siRNA and shRNA sequences were then added to non-ontology data dictionary with appropriate SO terms (*SO_0000646* and *SO_0002031*, respectively). *RO_0002430* (“involved in negative regulation of”) has been selected in this case.
- “lncRNA-gene” from LncExpDB contain lncRNA cells with comma-separated multiple values that have to be processed similarly to snoDB ones. LncExpDB predicts lncRNA-gene interactions based on co-expression networks. Valid relations are identified by using FDR and Pearson correlation coefficient ($FDR < 0.01$ and $|r| \geq 0.5$). Generic *RO_0002434* (“interacts with”) term has been used.
- From TBDB, “riboswitch-biologic process” and “riboswitch-protein” interactions have been considered. tRNA downstream proteins (mainly amino acid ligases and synthetasis) have been grounded to PRO terminology, whereas biological processes refers to GO Biological Process identifiers. *RO_0000056* (“participates in”) has been employed for biological processes relationships, whereas *RO_0002529* (“is downstream of sequence of”) for interactions with tRNA downstream proteins.
- “ribozyme-biological process” interactions from Ribocentre are retrieved by analyzing the literature for ribozyme sequences. We carefully analyzed articles contained in *Application.xlsx* and, whenever feasible, associated ribozyme molecules with GO BP terms. *RO_0000056* (“participates in”) has been considered.
- “viral RNA-ribozyme” interactions from ViroidDB contain viral RNA sequences that have been further subdivided into single stranded viral RNA (ssRNA), negative sense single stranded viral RNA (ssRNA-), double stranded viral RNA (dsRNA) and generic viral sequences. All viral RNA molecules categories have been added to non-ontology data dictionary via precise SO terms (e.g., *SO_0001200* – “negative sense ssRNA viral sequence” – term for representing ssRNA- molecules). *RO_0002526* (“overlaps sequence of”) has been selected for representing “viral RNA-ribozyme” relations.
- “protein-, miRNA-, and mRNA-extracellular form” relations from Vesciclepedia have

been considered. As before, we have only kept human ncRNA sequences and grounded extracellular form concepts to GO Cellular Component terminology (e.g., “exosome” to *GO_0070062*, term that has this exact meaning). *RO_0001018* (“contained in”) has been employed.

- Similarly to Vesciclepedia, extracellular forms from “circRNA-extracellular form” interactions from miRandola have been mapped to GO Cellular Component terminology. circRNA molecules in miRandola only circulates in the blood (represented by *GO_0072562* term). As in the previous point, *RO_0001018* (“contained in”) has been selected for representing this kind of interactions.

4.3.2 New mappings

New mappings has been added to ensure common semantics for identifiers in RNA-KG with respect to the preliminary version presented in Section 2.3.2. They have been created by considering bio-ontology classes labels (see Listing 4.1 for an example), directly downloaded from public RNA-based data sources (see Listing 4.2 for an example), or manually built (see Listing 4.3 for an example).

```

1 # Get ontology classes labels
2 chebi_label = gets_ontology_class_labels(chebi_graph)[0]
3
4 chebi_dict = {str(k): {str(i).split('/')[0] for i in v} for k, v in chebi_label.items()}
5
6 with open(unprocessed_data_location + 'DESC_CHEBI_MAP.txt', 'w') as outfile:
7     for k, v in chebi_dict.items():
8         outfile.write(str(k) + '\t' + str(v).replace('{', '').replace('\t', ' ').replace('}', '')) + '\n')
9
10 # DESC_CHEBI_MAP.txt stores rows as: dodeca-2,10-diyne CHEBI_3782

```

Listing 4.1: Method for getting ontology classes labels applied to ChEBI terms. “gets_ontology_class_labels” method is implemented in Listing 2.17.

```

1 data_downloader('https://www.mirbase.org/ftp/CURRENT/aliases.txt.zip',
2                 unprocessed_data_location)
3
4 mirna_mirbase_map = pd.read_csv(unprocessed_data_location + 'aliases.txt', sep="\t", header=None)
5
6 mirna_mirbase_map[1] = mirna_mirbase_map[1].str[:-1]
7
8 mirna_mirbase_map[1] = mirna_mirbase_map[1].str.split(';')
9 mirna_mirbase_map = mirna_mirbase_map.explode(1)
10
11 mirna_mirbase_map[[1,0]].to_csv(processed_data_location + 'MIRNA_MIRBASE_MAP.txt', header=None, sep='\t', index=None)
12
13 # MIRNA_MIRBASE_MAP.txt stores rows as: cel-let-7L MI0000001

```

Listing 4.2: miRNA mapping in RNA-KG.

```

1 cancer_mondo_map = pd.DataFrame(data=[[ 'ACC', 'MONDO_0004971' ], [ 'BLCA', 'MONDO_0004163' ],
2 [ 'BRCA', 'MONDO_0006256' ], [ 'CESC', 'MONDO_0005131' ],
3 [ 'CHOL', 'MONDO_0019087' ], [ 'COAD', 'MONDO_0002271' ],
4 [ 'DLBC', 'MONDO_0018905' ], [ 'ESCA', 'MONDO_0019086' ],
5 [ 'GBM', 'MONDO_0018177' ], [ 'HNSC', 'MONDO_0010150' ],
6 [ 'KICH', 'MONDO_0017885' ], [ 'KIRC', 'MONDO_0005005' ],
7 [ 'KIRP', 'MONDO_0017884' ], [ 'LGG', 'MONDO_0005499' ],
8 [ 'LIHC', 'MONDO_0007256' ], [ 'LUAD', 'MONDO_0005061' ],
9 [ 'LUSC', 'MONDO_0005097' ], [ 'MESO', 'MONDO_0005065' ],
10 [ 'OV', 'MONDO_0006046' ], [ 'PAAD', 'MONDO_0006047' ],
11 [ 'PCPG', 'MONDO_0035540' ], [ 'PRAD', 'MONDO_0005082' ],
12 [ 'READ', 'MONDO_0002169' ], [ 'SARC', 'MONDO_0005089' ],
13 [ 'SKCM', 'MONDO_0005012' ], [ 'STAD', 'MONDO_0005036' ],
14 [ 'TGCT', 'MONDO_0010108' ], [ 'THCA', 'MONDO_0015075' ],
15 [ 'THYM', 'MONDO_0006456' ], [ 'UCEC', 'MONDO_0000553' ],
16 [ 'UCS', 'MONDO_0006485' ], [ 'UVM', 'MONDO_0006486' ]
17 ]
18
19 cancer_mondo_map.to_csv(processed_data_location + 'TCGA_MONDO_MAP.txt', header=None, sep='\t', index=None)

```

Listing 4.3: Script for manually mapping TCGA [248] cancer identifiers to Mondo terms.

4.3.3 Grounding non-ontology data

Non-ontology RNA-based data are manually added to dictionary *subclass_construction_map.pkl*; an example of how this occurs is shown in Listing 4.4. Whenever feasible, SO terms have been used for grounding non-ontology data to ensure compatibility with HDMM (see also Table 3.5). VO and ChEBI have also been used.

```

1 # Provided by PKL ecosystem
2 data_downloader(processed_url+'subclass_construction_map.pkl', '../resources/
   construction_approach/')
3
4 # Load data
5 nonO_data = pd.read_pickle(r'../resources/construction_approach/'+
   subclass_construction_map.pkl')
6
7 mature_mirna = mirna_mirbase_map[mirna_mirbase_map[0].str.startswith('MIMAT')]
8 mature_mirna['SO'] = [['SO_0000276']] * len(mature_mirna)
9
10 mirna_nonO = mature_mirna.drop(1, axis=1).set_index(0).to_dict()
11 nonO_data = {**nonO_data, **mirna_nonO['SO']}
12
13 with open('../resources/construction_approach/'+subclass_construction_map.pkl', 'wb') as
   handle:
14     pickle.dump(nonO_data, handle, protocol=pickle.HIGHEST_PROTOCOL)

```

Listing 4.4: Python script for adding new non-ontology mature miRNA-based data. *SO_0000276* term is labelled as “miRNA” in the SO.

4.4 RNA-KG topological analysis

In this last section, we will provide some topological properties of RNA-KG computed by means of GRAPE Python 3 Library. Topological properties are analyzed both from computational and biological sides, trying to understand if a biological reason stands behind a topological feature of RNA-KG.

4.4.1 The GRAPE library

GRAPE (Graph Representation leArning, Predictions and Evaluation) is a powerful graph processing and embedding library, designed to scale with big graphs. GRAPE consists of two main modules: Ensmallen and Embiggen, which are designed to work synergistically, with Ensmallen handling graph loading, pre-processing and processing operations, and providing training data to the node embedding and classifier models in Embiggen. Both modules are designed to reduce computational time and space by utilizing optimized data structures and parallel computation. Ensmallen is implemented in Rust [132] and provides efficient graph loading and processing capabilities. It utilizes both traditional map-reduce thread-based parallelism and branch-less Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD) parallelism, resulting in a substantial speedup for graph loading and processing operations. Ensmallen also employs a compact data structure that enables fast rank and select operations with minimal memory usage. Ensmallen also provides a fast computation of first and second-order random walks, as well as a novel approximated weighted first and second-order random-walk algorithm, allowing for the processing of graphs with high-degree nodes. This capability is crucial for managing graphs that would be otherwise infeasible to process using exact random walk algorithms. Thanks to the aforementioned features, Ensmallen is capable of generating billions of 100-length random walk samples per minute, which can then be used to leverage the accuracy of random-walk-based graph-embedding methods, therefore producing better results when the computed embeddings are used in the context of graph representation learning algorithms.

Ensmallen feeds the embeddings to Embiggen, which leverages TensorFlow [2] and GPU computing for efficient implementation of node and edge embedding algorithms. The obtained embeddings are highly accurate so that they enhance the performance of graph representation learning techniques provided by GRAPE, and have the potential to improve knowledge in several research fields. Indeed, the embeddings can be used for edge and node label prediction tasks, as well as unsupervised clustering analysis and visualization of complex graphs.

In addition to the core functionalities, GRAPE offers various resources such as Monte

Property	Description
singleton node	a node disconnected from all other nodes
chain	a path of nodes with unique degree 2 (in which self-loop and multi-edges are ignored) connecting two strongly connected components of the graph
isomorphic groups	nodes with exactly the same neighbors and node types (if present in the graph). Nodes in such groups are topologically indistinguishable, that is swapping their ID would not change the graph topology
dendritic tree	a tree-like structure starting from a root node that is part of another strongly connected component
tendrils	a path from a node of degree one to a strongly connected component
dendritic tendrils star	a dendritic tree with a depth ≥ 1 , where the arms of the star are tendrils

Table 4.4: Graph characteristics that can be extracted by GRAPE

Carlo holdouts mechanism, algorithms for computing random and minimum spanning arborescence and connected components, parallel computation of betweenness centrality, graph filtering methods, and algebraic set operations. It also provides access to a curated collection of 80,000 commonly used graphs from the literature and other sources, standardized interfaces allowing a straightforward integration of third-party libraries, 61 node embedding methods, 25 inference models, and 3 modular pipelines for graph processing and embedding. Considered KGs includes PheKnowLator built HDMM and Natural Product KG (NP-KG [231]), KG-Microbe [114], and CovidKG.ORG. We exploited GRAPE facilities to embed, visualize, and extract relevant topological characteristics of the current version of RNA-KG. Moreover, GRAPE offers simple-to-implement interfaces that can be used by any user to ingest their own graph representation learning technique into the GRAPE resource. Further, the availability of already implemented standardized comparison pipelines allows any user to perform an objective comparative evaluation that follows the FAIR principles.

GRAPE is designed to be versatile and can be deployed on different hardware architectures, ranging from standard notebooks to High-Performance-Computing clusters. It offers multiple time-memory trade-off settings to accommodate available resources. With few instructions, GRAPE is able to point out degree centrality (the node degree is defined as number of edges incident in a node), node types, edge types, and topological oddities. A topological oddity is a set of nodes in the graph that may be derived by an error during the generation of the edge list of the graph and, depending on the task, could bias the results of topology-based models. Topological oddities may be of help in identifying biological and biomedical KG inconsistency from a topological point of view. Table 4.4 shows some of those that can be identified in a graph by GRAPE.

Extensive experimental evaluations demonstrate the superior speed and performance of GRAPE compared to other graph-processing libraries. It achieves orders of magnitude speedup and competitive results in edge and node label prediction problems. The GRAPE software and a tutorial for practical usage are available at the following link: <https://github.com/AnacletoLAB/grape>.

4.4.2 Extracting the characteristics of RNA-KG by GRAPE

Once RNA-KG node types, edge types have been converted in CSV file, we import RNA-KG into the GRAPE environment to retrieve relevant topological information. Listing 4.5 reports the GRAPE *Graph* object used for storing RNA-KG current version. To obtain an unweighted KG, *weights_column_number* parameter has been set to *None*. GRAPE efficiently imports RNA-KG in less than a minute on a desktop computer. Code for importing RNA-KG in GRAPE is available at the following link: https://github.com/AnacletoLAB/RNA-KG/RNA-KG_GRAPE.ipynb.

```
1 RNA_KG = Graph.from_csv(  
2     # node types parameters  
3     node_type_path = "ntypeslist.csv",  
4     node_list_node_types_column="type",  
5     node_types_column="type",  
6     node_type_list_header=True,  
7     node_list_numeric_node_type_ids = True,  
8  
9     # edge types parameters  
10    edge_type_path = "etypeslist.csv",  
11    edge_types_column="type",  
12    edge_type_list_header=True,  
13    edge_type_list_separator="," ,  
14  
15    # Edges related parameters  
16    edge_path="RNA-KG.csv",  
17    edge_list_header=True,  
18    sources_column_number=0,  
19    destinations_column_number=2,  
20    edge_list_numeric_node_ids=True,  
21    weights_column_number=None,  
22    edge_list_edge_types_column_number=1,  
23    edge_list_numeric_edge_type_ids = True,  
24  
25    # Nodes related parameters  
26    node_path="nodeslist.csv",  
27    node_list_header=True,  
28    nodes_column="name",  
29  
30    # Graph related parameters  
31    directed=True,  
32    name='RNA-KG',  
33    verbose=True,  
34 )
```

Listing 4.5: GRAPE *Graph* object for RNA-KG.

GRAPE points out that the minimum node degree is 0, the maximum node degree is 16.32K, the mode degree is 2, the mean degree is 9.82, and the node degree median is 2. Moreover, the clustering coefficient is equal to 15,486.58, the average clustering coefficient is around 0.025, the average Jaccard coefficient score is around 0.048, the density is around 1.31×10^{-5} , the transitivity is around 0.0034, and the diameter is equal to 49. The two nodes with the highest degree centrality are all nodes with type GO. They are *GO_0005634* (degree 16.32K), *GO_0070062* (degree 13.43K), and *GO_1990742* (degree 10.79K). They are nodes related to cellular compartments (nucleus, cytosol, extracellular exosome, and microvescicle respectively). This makes sense since during RNA-KG construction we put into relation many proteins and RNA molecules with cellular compartments they are usually located or contained in.

From a biological point of view, RNA-KG relevant common node types are protein (226.97K nodes, 36.27%), chemical (164.52K nodes, 26.29%), GO (43.16K nodes, 6.90%), disease (23.16K nodes, 3.70%), sequence (16.40K nodes, 2.62%), riboswitch (16.21K nodes, 2.59%), and tRF (10.03K nodes, 1.60%). Fig. 4.6 depicts node types distribution of RNA-KG. “geneOrRNA” label is used for naming ncRNA molecules without a well-recognized and standardized identification system (i.e., we employ Entrez Gene IDs for representing these sequences). Specifically, this label is used for genes, mRNAs, snoRNAs, snRNAs, lncRNAs, and circRNAs.

From a biological point of view, RNA-KG relevant common edge types are molecularly interacts with (1.25M edges, 20.29%), the generic interacts with (1.24M edges, 20.09%), regulates activity of (423.08K edges, 6.88%), has participant and participates in (394.63K edges, 6.42% both), is substance that treats and is treated by substance (166.92K edges, 2.72% both), is downstream of sequence of and is upstream of sequence of (147.76K edges, 2.41% both), located in and location of (81.83K edges, 1.32% both), and contains and contained in (57.51K edges, 0.93% both). We can notice “has participant-participates in”, “is downstream of sequence of-is upstream of sequence of”, “is substance that treats-is treated by substance”, “located in-location of”, and “contains-contained in” couples have the same amount of edges since they are one the RO inverse of the other. Fig. 4.5 shows the distribution of the ten most common edge types. The obtained subclasses of edges correspond to the ontological “PART_OF” relationships identified during the integration of bio-ontologies through PheKnowLator ecosystem.

Topological oddities obtained through GRAPE are now described by providing a possible explanation in biological terms. GRAPE has detected 229 *singleton nodes* in the graph (0.04%) that correspond to the 229 RO terms obtained from the integration of RO into RNA-KG via PheKnowLator. They are singletons because their semantics is only used for labeling connections between biological and biomedical entities.

Figure 4.5: Edges types' distributions in RNA-KG.

GRAPE has detected 442 *isomorphic node groups* in RNA-KG, involving a total of 8.72K nodes (1.39%) and 304.49K edges (4.95%), with the largest one involving 1.04K nodes and 33.31K edges. The detected isomorphic node groups with larger size involve riboswitches and tRFs. This makes sense since in RNA-KG many riboswitches are associated with the same tRNA-downstream proteins, and tRFs stem from the same tRNA molecules. An example is the group with 194 nodes (degree 57) with node type tRF, that contains *tsRNA-Leu-i-0309*, *tsRNA-Leu-i-0408*, *tsRNA-Leu-i-0390*, *tsRNA-Leu-5-0075*, *tsRNA-Leu-i-0299* and other 189 tRF molecules originating from tRNA sequences encoding the essential amino acid leucine (*Leu*). Other isomorphic node groups of biological relevance are mainly related to proteins encoding tRNA ligases or synthases that encode, as stated before, tRNA-downstream protein connected with tRF sequences.

On the other hand, GRAPE has detected 410 *isomorphic edge groups* in RNA-KG, involving a total of 79.78K nodes (12.75%), with the largest one involving 6.07K nodes. The detected isomorphic edge groups, sorted by decreasing size, pointed out by GRAPE are protein-riboswitch and riboswitch-protein interactions. An example from the largest isomorphic edge group component (1.12K edges component) is *PR_Q8RXK8-2-NPSCZVV* interaction, where *PR_Q8RXK8-2* is an isoleucine-tRNA ligase and *NPSCZVV* is a riboswitch whose tRNA-downstream protein is an isoleucine.

4.4.3 RNA-KG embedding visualization by GRAPE

GRAPE allows the user to visualize animations of different kinds of embedding. Thus, we can obtain bidimensional t-SNE images representing RNA-KG edge and node types by instantiating a GraphVisualizer object (Embiggen module) and calling appropriate

Figure 4.6: Nodes types' distributions in RNA-KG.

methods as in Listing 4.6. Fig. 4.7 depicts a bidimensional view of common node types of RNA-KG, whereas Fig. 4.8 depicts a bidimensional view of common edge types of RNA-KG. They both make use of First-order Large-scale Information Network Embedding (LINE [232]) implemented in GRAPE. We avoid to represent inverse relationships in the embedding space since they would overlap (inverse relationships involve the same entities connected with two edges whose directions are swapped).

```

1 vis = GraphVisualizer(
2     graph=RNA_KG,
3     n_components=2,
4     decomposition_method="TSNE"
5     edge_embedding_method="Hadamard",
6     verbose=True,
7     # Automatically, since LINE learns a cosine, the visualization tool
8     # would dispatch a Cosine-distance based TSNE. This would use the sklearn
9     # implementation, which is terribly slow.
10    # Therefore, we force it to use the Euclidean distance
11    # and therefore the Multicore TSNE implementation (when available).
12    decomposition_kwargs=dict(metric="euclidean")
13 )
14
15 embedding = FirstOrderLINEEnsmallen().fit_transform(RNA_KG)
16 vis.fit_edges(embedding)
17 vis.fit_nodes(embedding)
18 vis.plot_edge_types()
19 vis.plot_node_types()

```

Listing 4.6: RNA-KG visualization with GRAPE.

Node types RNA-KG First-order LINE

Figure 4.7: Bidimensional view of RNA-KG node types embedded by First-order LINE with GRAPE.

Edge types RNA-KG First-order LINE Hadamard

Figure 4.8: Bidimensional view of RNA-KG edge types embedded by First-order LINE with GRAPE.

Conclusions and Future Work

This thesis reports the initial results of an ongoing project for the creation of a biomedical KG for the representation of non-coding RNA molecules and their relationships made available in different public data sources. We have described different approaches and techniques that have been used in the biomedical context for the integration of heterogeneous data sources into an integrated KG presenting different kinds of nodes and edges and whose content and structure are described by means of domain ontologies. Starting from a biological description of the different kinds of coding and non-coding RNA molecules, we have identified more than 50 public data sources containing these molecules and their main characteristics have been pointed out. Finally, a meta-graph has been realized for representing the different types of relationships that can be identified and then exploited for conducting different kinds of AI analysis.

The current release of RNA-KG can be accessed through a SPARQL endpoint for which we used an AllegroGraph triplestore [73] that offers a graphical user interface for performing queries. The endpoint is constantly updated and available at the following link: <http://fiavel.anacleto.di.unimi.it:10035/#/repositories/RNA-KG>. The code used for the integration of the different sources is available on AnacletoLAB GitHub repository at the following link: <https://github.com/AnacletoLAB/RNA-KG>.

Currently, we are working on further integrating specific databases on RNA. We would also like to develop graphical facilities for supporting the user in the data acquisition process and thus reducing the manual effort required for mapping the data available in the different data sources into RNA-KG [32]. Specifically, we would like to consider innovative approaches for populating knowledge bases conforming to a given schema. Among them, SPIRES [42] is a knowledge extraction tool that relies on Large Language Models to perform zero-shot learning, assisting manual knowledge curation and acquisition, while supporting validation with publicly-available databases and ontologies.

Secondly, we wish to enable reasoning on top of RNA-KG through cutting-edge AI graph

representation learning algorithms [254, 257]. The methods will rely on graph representation learning approaches based on Graph Neural Networks and Random Walks that take into account the heterogeneity of the graph and the presence of an ontology that describes the possible relationships existing among the involved entities.

Finally, the developed RNA-KG will be validated with experts in pharmacology within UNIMI and across different international research centers such as Charité Universitätsmedizin in Berlin (Germany), Columbia University in the City of New York (USA), and the Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (USA). Prioritization of bioactive molecules whose biological profile is central in RNA-KG could constitute the basis for further molecular studies such as substrate binding and target-ligand molecular docking in silico predictions that could be performed in collaboration with cheminformatics research groups in the context of the National Center for RNA drugs. RNA-KG would also prove to be useful towards the identification and validation of new RNA-drugs and in the construction of toxicity-related predictive models or MoA studies to support the discovery of novel RNA drugs. The entire process of development will be empowered by easy-to-use applications for users with different backgrounds (i.e., biological, biomedical, biochemical, and pharmaceutical) for ingesting new validated data into KG, and retrieving or inferring meaningful information from RNA-KG.

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